

Flow-Induced Vibrations in Nuclear Power Plants

Educational Material for WP6 by NRG and TU Delft

Version N°1
12 / 2023

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Document information

Grant Agreement / Proposal ID	101060826
Project Title	Gathering expertise On Vibration ImpaKt In Nuclear power Generation
Project Acronym	GO-VIKING
Scientific Coordinator	Angel Papukchiev, mailto:Angel.Papukchiev@grs.de , GRS
Project starting date (duration)	1st June 2022 – 31st May 2026 (48 Months)
Related Work Package	WP6
Related Task(s)	T6.1 Educational Material
Lead Organisation	VKI
Contributing Partner(s)	NRG, TU Delft
Due Date	31-5-2024
Submission Date	1-12-2023
Dissemination level	PU

History

Date	Version	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Comments
1-12-2023	1	K. Zwijsen		

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Introduction

With an increasing worldwide human population comes an increasing energy demand. Different conventional and non-conventional sources of energy are available and made use of. This has a direct link to global warming. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) warns humanity about the effects of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways.^[1] Nuclear energy is a way to transition to a world with low carbon footprint as pointed by many international studies especially when affordability of energy production is considered.^{[1]–[7]}

An advantage of nuclear power plants is its capability of producing electrical power almost year-round with the exception of a 3 week period of refuelling and maintenance. For economic benefit, it is desired that the plants run without any unplanned outages. Another reason for this is the possibility of the nuclear reactor to be unable to restart owing to the build-up of Xenon. After a power decrease or shutdown, it may take up to about 3 days before a typical reactor is able to override the effects of Xenon. Translating the time loss into money at a rate of 1 million euro per day,^{[8],[9]} the desire to avoid outages is made obvious.

A leading reason for the downtime is owed to damage as a result of Flow Induced Vibrations (FIV). FIV has been pointed to be a cause of fatigue problems, stress corrosion, cracking, fretting wear and other possible failure modes in nuclear power plants.^{[9],[10]} Increasing energy demand leads to change of coolant, its flow rate or changes in component material and/or dimensions leading to more prominent FIV.^[11] With this in mind, an introduction to nuclear power plants and associated FIV mechanisms is provided in the following sections of this chapter.

1.1. Nuclear Power Plant

A schematic sketch of the secondary circuit of a generic steam-based power plant is shown in [Figure 1.1](#). The steam generated in the steam generator (S.G) turns the blades of a turbine (T) which is connected to a generator (G) thereby obtaining electrical energy. After performing work, the steam is condensed in a condenser (C) making use of a water body nearby or a cooling tower (C.T). The condensed steam is pumped back to the steam generator via a pump (P) for the cycle to be complete.

Figure 1.1: Schematic Sketch of a Generic Power Plant

A nuclear power plant makes use of nuclear fission to obtain the energy for converting water to steam in the steam generator. This energy transfer can be done directly as in a Boiling Water Reactor (BWR) or indirectly using a primary circuit involving a separate reactor such as the Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR). Nuclear reactors can be classified based on the type of nuclear reaction, moderator, coolant, phase of fuel, generation, shape of core and use. Based on the type of nuclear reaction, nuclear reactors can be classified as thermal neutron reactors and fast neutron reactors. Thermal neutron reactors employ slowed or thermal neutrons by the action of moderator material to increase the probability of fission of an enriched fuel such as uranium-235. Fast neutron reactors employ fast neutrons to cause fission without the use of a moderator, thereby acting on natural or low-enriched fuel to produce another nuclear fuel such as uranium-238 forming plutonium-239 which is better at fissioning than uranium-235.

The Institution of Electrical Engineers have classified the nuclear reactors based on the coolant-moderator combination as follows:^[12]

- Gas Cooled & Graphite Moderated - GCR, HTR, AGR
- Hard Water Cooled & Moderated - PHWR, CANDU
- Light Water Cooled & Moderated – PWR, BWR, VVER
- Light Water Cooled & Graphite Moderated – LWGR, RBMK
- Liquid Metal Cooled – FBR, SFR, LFR

Pioneering work on Gas Cooled Reactors (GCR) has been done in the United Kingdom with their fleet of Advanced Gas-cooled Reactors (AGR) that use CO₂ with a graphite moderator. Further development has led to High Temperature Reactors (HTR) which typically uses helium gas as a coolant and a graphite moderator.

Water cooled reactors use either light or heavy water as the coolant. The coolant can also be a moderator or a separate graphite moderator could be used. The most common types are the earlier mentioned PWR and BWR. Besides the difference in the extra circuit, PWR employs light water that is pressured upto about 150 bar which prevents the coolant from boiling in the primary circuit. In both types of such reactors, refuelling has to be done during an outage. This has consequences for the availability (up time) of the reactor. In order to minimise the down-time of a reactor, on-line refuelling, i.e. refuelling during operation, was targeted in other reactor designs. In Russia, this led to the water-cooled graphite-moderated RBMK reactors. In Canada this led to the so-called CANDU reactors, a Pressurized Heavy Water Reactor (PHWR) type. Besides on-line refuelling, these reactors allow, through the use of heavy water as coolant and moderator, the use of natural uranium, avoiding the need for fuel enrichment required for most other reactors.

For fast neutron reactors, it is desired to split the uranium-239 isotope instead of the uranium-235. To achieve this, moderators are not used in so-called Fast Breeder Reactors (FBR). The most commonly applied coolant is sodium but given its chemically reactive nature, lead and lead-bismuth have also been employed. According to the latest IAEA Power Reactor Information System (PRIS) data^{[13],[14]}, the following distribution of reactors in operation and in construction reveals PWR to be the most common type of nuclear reactor.

Figure 1.2: Types and electrical capacity of reactors used and under construction worldwide (as of 18 Oct. 2020)^{[13],[14]}

1.2. Flow Induced Vibration

The term Flow Induced Vibration (FIV) is used to describe all the phenomena that are associated with the response of structures immersed in a flow. In literature for internal flows, the term FIV is used for stationary (statistically steady) flow where interaction is mainly one-way from fluid to solid and Fluid Structure Interaction (FSI) is used for two-way interactions in unsteady flows.^[15] However, in this report, both terms are used interchangeably for nuclear applications.

Different parts of the nuclear reactor can vibrate due to entirely different excitation mechanisms. Figure 1.3 shows two important areas of concern for a PWR: the pressure vessel (reactor) and the steam generator. Although a vertical steam generator is shown here, horizontal steam generators do exist as have been employed in VVER, a Russian-designed light water cooled and moderated reactor. In fact, they are better than the vertical type on account of easy sludge handling.^[16] As far as FIV is concerned, the flow around fuel rods is axial whereas the steam generator tubes have both axial and cross flow. The type of flow along the fuel rods could be single or two-phase. In particular, steam generators have single phase cross flow at the entry, two-phase axial flow in the middle and two-phase cross flow at the U-bend. Such flow conditions decide the nature of interaction between the structure and the fluid.

Figure 1.3: Sketches of areas of interest for FIV in nuclear applications

Pettigrew et. al.^[18] provides the following classification of FIV mechanisms in nuclear applications:

1. **Fluid Elastic Instability (FEI):** This is a result of coupling between fluid-induced dynamic forces and the elastic vibration of structures. When the energy absorbed by structure from the fluid dynamic forces is higher than the energy dissipated by damping, instability occurs. This occurs beyond a certain critical velocity.
2. **Periodic Wake Shedding:** This occurs very readily behind structures in cross flow. With periodic wake or vortex shedding, periodic fluid forces act on the structure which set it to vibrate if the shedding frequency lies in proximity to its natural frequency. The vibration so occurring is termed as Vortex Induced Vibration (VIV).
3. **Turbulence Excitation:** Turbulence generated locally by the fluid as it flows around a structure (near-field excitation) and that generated by upstream components such as inlet nozzles, elbows, etc. (far-field excitation) can create random pressure fluctuations around the surface of components causing them to vibrate. This vibration is termed as Turbulence Induced Vibration (TIV) and is of prime importance in axial flows.
4. **Acoustic Resonance:** It occurs when the vortex shedding frequency matches with the natural frequency of the acoustic cavity formed by the structures surrounding the primary structure. This is of importance in single phase axial flows as well as tube bundles subjected to gas cross flow.

Figure 1.4 relates the vibration excitation mechanisms to different flow situations in nuclear reactor applications and gives their relative importance. It is observed that for single phase axial flow, acoustic resonance and turbulence excitation are prime suspects for the cause of damage. For steam generators, which generally have cross flow at the entry and the U-bend, fluid elastic instability is the prime suspect for damage. In particular, for liquid flows, periodic shedding and turbulence induced vibrations also have a role to play.

Flow situation	Fluidelastic instability	Periodic shedding	Turbulence excitation	Acoustic resonance
Axial flow				
Internal				
Liquid	*	—	**	***
Gas	*	—	*	***
Two-phase	*	—	**	*
External				
Liquid	**	—	**	***
Gas	*	—	*	***
Two-phase	*	—	**	*
Cross flow				
Single cylinders				
Liquid	—	***	**	*
Gas	—	**	*	*
Two-Phase	—	*	**	—
Tube Bundle				
Liquid	***	**	**	*
Gas	***	*	*	***
Two-phase	***	*	**	—

***Most important.
 **Should be considered.
 *Less likely.
 —, Does not apply.

Steam generator
 Fuel rods
 Steam generator and fuel rods

Figure 1.4: Vibration Excitation Mechanisms (Amended from [18])

Figure 1.5 reveals how these mechanisms may be superimposed to get the vibrational response from a structure. It is observed that FEI is the most destructive mechanism with VIV and acoustic resonance having a specific range in which the destruction is maximum, and random vibration or TIV being present in the entire range of flow velocities with its detrimental effect increasing with flow velocity.

Figure 1.5: Vibrational Response as a superimposition of different FIV mechanisms^[19]

Another way to classify fluid-structure interaction excitation mechanisms given by Rockwell^[20] is based on how they are produced. The categories under this classification are listed below.

1. **Extraneously Induced Excitation:** This is caused by fluctuations in flow velocities or pressure that are independent of any instability due to structural movement except the added mass and fluid damping effects. The exciting force is mostly random but may also be periodic.
2. **Instability Induced Excitation:** The instability is intrinsic to the flow system created by the structure being considered. An example of this would be vortex induced vibrations. There is also a possibility of control mechanisms that can strengthen the excitation such as resonance and fluidelastic feedback.
3. **Movement Induced Excitation:** This occurs due to fluctuating forces that arise due to the movement of a vibrating body. These type of vibrations are thus aptly named self-excited.

Based on the nature of vibrations, Weaver^[21] classifies FIV as (a) forced vibrations induced by turbulence, (b) self-controlled vibrations for which some periodicity exists in the flow field that is independent of the movement of the structure, and (c) self-excited vibrations. Blevins^[22] uses a phenomenological way of classification, grouping the vibrations as induced by (a) steady flow and (b) unsteady flow. For this report, the classification given by Pettigrew et. al.^[18] is deemed more useful in the context of nuclear applications.

1.3. Organization of the Report

In this chapter, an introduction was provided to nuclear power plants, its types and associated FIV problems and mechanisms. The following 4 chapters ([chapter 2](#)-[chapter 5](#)) give more details about each of the mechanisms in the order of FEI, VIV, acoustic resonance and TIV. Since the report is more concerned with numerical simulation of FIV problems, the relevant FSI theory is provided in [chapter 6](#).

2

Fluid Elastic Instability

Fluid Elastic Instability (FEI) is characterized by an abrupt rise in dynamic response for a small increment in flow velocity. The velocity at which this instability occurs is called the critical velocity, above which rapid failure may occur. FEI is seen as the excitation mechanism that has the greatest destructive potential. This was also made evident from [Figure 1.5](#). Therefore, a lot of attention is given to its modelling and prediction in order to avoid operating in this regime.

The disastrous effects of FEI in heat exchangers is shown in [Figure 2.1](#). Impacting of tubes with the baffle supports wore them down till they burst. In some cases, they cut through the baffle supports creating a free double-span leading to higher amplitude vibration. In the case of a sodium–water heat exchanger, the Na-H₂O chemical reaction caused additional devastation.

Figure 2.1: A compendium of characteristic damage to heat-exchanger tube arrays due to fluid elastic instability:(a) from a CANDU steam generator; (b) from Na-H₂O steam generator; (c) from a steam-steam heat exchanger;(d) from a steam condenser;(e) from another heat exchanger; based on cases analysed in [23] by [9]

2.1. Mechanisms of FEI

The nature of FEI can be depicted as a feedback mechanism between structural response and its associated fluid forces. A small structural displacement, caused by let's say turbulence for instance, alters the flow pattern and thereby the fluid forces which in turn leads to an enhanced displacement and so on.

This instability now has to be classified as static or dynamic. In particular, for dynamic instability, Chen^[24] classified it as due to vibrational velocity dependent forces (damping controlled mechanism or negative damping) or displacement dependent forces (stiffness controlled mechanism).

A more fundamental way to understand this classification is given by Price^[25]. Consider a single Degree of Freedom (1-DoF) simple harmonically oscillating cylinder which vibrates with an amplitude X and circular frequency ω . Its displacement x is given by

$$x = X \sin(\omega t) \quad (2.1)$$

Assuming linear quasi-static fluid dynamics, the fluid force acting on the cylinder is given by

$$F = Cx \quad (2.2)$$

where C is a fluid stiffness term proportional to the dynamic pressure of the flow. The work done by the fluid force per cycle of oscillation is given by

$$W = \int_0^{2\pi/\omega} \dot{x}F dt \quad (2.3)$$

Substituting Equation 2.1 and Equation 2.2 in Equation 2.3 gives $W = 0$. The system is conservative and the fluid force can't lead to a dynamic instability. A negative C can overcome the positive structural stiffness and thereby induce a static instability.

There are three ways that can lead to $W < 0$ implying dynamic instability:

1. For the same 1-DoF system, there exists a phase difference between the cylinder displacement and fluid force generated thereby, which now has a component in phase with the cylinder vibrational velocity: a non-conservative fluid-damping force. This is a simple damping controlled mechanism.
2. Consider now the system with 2-DoF along with a phase difference. Equation 2.1 can be considered but with a phase in the sine term and x and X being vectors. The fluid stiffness term will accordingly be a square matrix which if non-symmetric will lead to a non-conservative system. Since the destabilizing fluid forces are in-phase with the cylinder displacement, this mechanism is referred as stiffness controlled.
3. A final possibility exists when, because of non-linearities, the fluid force is hysteric and its magnitude depends on the direction of cylinder motion. A classic example is the jet-switch model by Roberts.^{[26],[27]}

2.2. Fluid Elastic Instability Models

Until the 1960's, FIV due to FEI were wrongly attributed to Vortex Induced Vibration (VIV). The first work discovering the self-excitation mechanism in a staggered row of cylinders under cross flow for in-line vibration was by Roberts^[26] in his PhD. A theoretical prediction of the earlier mentioned critical velocity was proposed by Roberts^[27] based on a jet-switch phenomenon. Not all FEI vibrations are in-line but a majority of them show whirling motion. In this area, a breakthrough was made by Connors^[28] in 1970 with the famous Connors' equation that connected the critical velocity with a mass-damping parameter (which is half the Scruton Number):

$$\frac{U_{pc}}{f_n D} = K \left(\frac{m\delta}{\rho D^2} \right)^a \quad (2.4)$$

where U_{pc} is the effective critical flow velocity (also called gap or pitch or intertube velocity). f_n , m and δ represent the cylinder natural frequency, mass per unit length and logarithmic decrement of the cylinder free vibration respectively. Connors had provided a value of $a = 0.5$ and $K = 9.9$ from his work which was based on a single row of cylinders. Blevins^[29], for a single row of cylinders, had arrived at the same expression as Connors but with a different constant K . However, when these were applied in the design of heat exchangers, FEI failure still occurred.

Connors^[30] in 1978 published his work on arrays revealing a constant value of $K = 2.7 - 3.9$. This means that the design using $K = 9.9$ was about 3 times too high than the actual critical velocity which explains the failure of earlier heat exchangers. As a guideline, a value of $K = 3.3$ is taken as is suggested by Pettigrew et. al.^[31] Figure 2.2 shows the compilation of experimental data on FEI in cross flow.

Figure 2.2: Experimental data on FEI in cross flow as compiled by Pettigrew et. al. [31]

It is to be noted that the damping parameter, δ is used quite interchangeably with $2\pi\zeta$ in literature but this is only an approximation which is valid for low damping ratio, ζ . Some authors have suggested that the mass ratio ($m/\rho D^2$) and damping parameter (δ) should be varied separately. This gives rise to the expression

$$\frac{U_{pc}}{f_n D} = K \left(\frac{m}{\rho D^2} \right)^a \delta^b \tag{2.5}$$

The values of K , a and b found by different authors for Equation 2.4 and Equation 2.5 were summarized by Chen^[32] and are shown in Table 2.1 and Table 2.2. Here, P/D is the pitch spacing to diameter ratio in an array.

Investigators	K	a	Remarks
Connors ^[28]	9.9	0.5	Tube row with T/D=1.42
Blevins ^[29]	$\frac{2(2\pi)^{0.5}}{(C_x C_y)^{0.25}}$	0.5	C_x and C_y are fluidelastic stiffness force coefficients
Chen ^[33]	$\alpha Re^{-0.25}$	0.5	Re is the Reynolds Number, α is a constant
Gross ^[34]	$4/\alpha$	1.0	For square array and α defined from fluid force
Gorman ^[35]	3.3	0.5	Suggested design guideline
Savkar ^[36]	$4.95(T/D)^2$	0.5	For triangular arrays
Connors ^[30]	$0.37+1.76(P/D)$	0.5	For square array, $1.41 \leq P/D \leq 2.12$
Pettigrew et. al. ^[31]	3.3	0.5	Suggested design guideline
Weaver and Grover ^[37]	7.1	0.21	Rotated triangular array, $P/D = 1.375$
Chen and Jendrzejczyk ^[38]	2.49-6.03	0.2-1.08	For various rectangular arrays and mixed array in water flow
Tanaka and Takahara ^[39]	3.0	0.75	For square array, $P/D = 2$

Table 2.1: Values of K and a in studies where critical flow velocity is a function of mass damping parameter^[32]

Investigators	K	a	b	Remarks
Païdoussis ^[40]		0.5	0.25	Using published data
Païdoussis ^[40]	$2.3 \left(\frac{P}{D} - 1\right)^{0.5}$	0.4	0.4	Including all data
Païdoussis ^[40]	$5.8 \left(\frac{P}{D} - 1\right)^{0.5}$	0.4	0.4	Excluding some data
Tanaka and Takahara ^[39]		0.5	0.5	For square array, $P/D = 1.33$, low density fluid
Tanaka and Takahara ^[39]		0.333	0.2	For square array, $P/D = 1.33$, high density fluid

Table 2.2: Values of K , a and b in studies where critical flow velocity is a function of mass ratio and damping^[32]

In 2001, Price^[41] investigated the use of Connors' equation and the variations thereof to predict FEI in cylinder arrays. It was suggested that mass ratio and damping should not be combined as a single mass-damping parameter. Furthermore, the influence of δ on U_{pc} was much less than what Connors' equation suggests. The most important conclusion from his review is that there is little justification in using Connors' equation, or variations thereof, to predict the velocity at which instability will occur. There are other models available in literature which aim to model FEI. These have been reviewed by Price^[25] and are categorized as:

- Jet Switch Model of Roberts^{[26],[27]}
- Semi-Analytical Models: eg. Lever & Weaver^[42], Yetisir & Weaver^[43]
- Quasi Steady Models: eg. Fung^[44], Gross^[34]
- CFD Models: eg. Stansby et. al.^[45], Hassan et. al.^[46]
- Quasi-Static Models: eg. Connors^{[28],[30]}, Blevins^{[29],[47]}
- Inviscid Models: eg. Païdoussis et. al.^[48], Dalton^[49]
- Unsteady Models: eg. Tanaka & Takahara^{[39],[50]}, Chen^[51]

Price^[25] concludes in his review that the models by Tanaka and Takahara^{[39],[50]} and Chen^[51] which employ measured unsteady fluid force coefficient data are the most accurate in capturing FEI. The downside is that this data is quite difficult to obtain and was made available only for one type of array and two values of P/D . Figure 2.3 shows their key results.

Figure 2.3: Theoretical boundary for FEI from unsteady models

There is a difference between the mechanism producing instability at high mass-damping parameter compared to low mass-damping parameter. This has been pointed out to be stiffness-controlled for high mass-damping parameter and damping-controlled for low mass-damping parameter.^{[24],[52]} Price^[25] also highlights the importance of phase-lag between cylinder motion and fluid forces on the cylinder itself and surrounding cylinders. For low mass-damping parameter, it is the leading destabilizing mechanism in fully flexible cylinders. The multiple stable-unstable regions seen in Figure 2.3b are also a result of this phase-lag. However, experimentally these multiple regions have not been observed due to the non-linear effects in heat exchangers. It is hoped that with the advancement in CFD, more accurate predictions will be made.

2.3. Added Mass, Damping and Stiffness

When a submerged structure vibrates or if a structure containing fluid vibrates (as in a steam generator of a PWR), the fluid in contact with the structure is forced to move. The induced fluid motion in turn generates a fluid force acting on the structure as a feedback. Such fluid-dynamic feedback effects should be taken into consideration in the analysis of FSI systems.

In the FIV analyses mainly used for practical design processes, empirical or analytical closed-form expressions of the fluid forces, which are obtained by experimental measurement, simplification of the structural geometry, or using potential flow theory, are usually used. These forces are then introduced in the equations of motion of the structure.^[19]

Figure 2.4: Typical FSI system^[19]

Consider the FSI system shown in Figure 2.4. The governing equation on the structure side is given by

$$m_s \ddot{x} + c_s \dot{x} + k_s x = F(\ddot{x}, \dot{x}, x) + F_f(t) \quad (2.6)$$

where x is the cylinder displacement, the dots denote derivatives with respect to time t , and m_s , c_s , k_s are the cylinder mass, structural damping coefficient and stiffness, respectively. On the right-hand side, the fluid forces are expressed as an unsteady force induced by cylinder motion and another extraneous fluid force that is independent of the cylinder motion. Taking the first-order Taylor series expansion of the first term, we have

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{\partial F}{\partial \ddot{x}} \ddot{x} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \dot{x} + \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} x + \dots \\ &\approx -m_a \ddot{x} - c_a \dot{x} - k_a x \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Substituting Equation 2.7 in Equation 2.6 gives

$$(m_s + m_a) \ddot{x} + (c_s + c_a) \dot{x} + (k_s + k_a) x = F_f(t) \quad (2.8)$$

The cylinder thus oscillates with additional terms in its mass, damping and stiffness. These additional terms are called added mass, added damping and added stiffness respectively. Given that the acceleration is usually in phase with the displacement, without a complete theoretical model of FSI, it is impossible to separate added stiffness and added mass.^[20] Therefore in literature for cross flows, quite some effort has been put in accurately estimating the added mass and damping. It is to be noted that the added stiffness term becomes highly important for low-speed flows and axial flow applications and requires special treatment.

Evaluating the added mass is important due its primary effect of reducing the natural frequency.^[19] If not accounted for, the calculated frequency will be overestimated which will lead to a decrease in safety margin. Another important component of the added mass is that due to cross-coupling.^[19] Cross-coupling is often observed for multi-DoF non-symmetric bodies where the translational and rotational motions interact with each other through the inertial forces. This is typical for tube-bundles.

The added mass is fairly simple to account for by approximating the fluid motion as potential flow. The added mass for a 2D cylinder in non-viscous, incompressible, infinite and still fluid is given by [32] as

$$m_a = \rho \frac{\pi}{4} d^2 \quad (2.9)$$

where m_a is the added mass per unit length, ρ is the fluid density and d is the diameter of the cylinder. The added mass coefficient C_M is the ratio of the added mass to the displaced fluid mass m_f . Here, the value turned out to be unity. The added mass coefficient is not always unity but rather depends on the body shape, the fluid viscosity, fluid compressibility, whether the fluid is still or flowing and the vibration amplitude, since flow separation and vortex shedding occur when the displacement amplitude is large relative to the cylinder diameter, even for the case of still fluid.^[19]

In particular, for tube arrays, Blevins gave an analytical formula to determine the coefficient of a flexible tube surrounded by rigid tubes. This is given in [53] as

$$C_M = \frac{((1 + 0.5P/D)P/D)^2 + 1}{((1 + 0.5P/D)P/D)^2 - 1} \quad (2.10)$$

Figure 2.5 reveals the influence of the type of array geometry on the added mass. It is revealed that decreasing P/D will lead to higher added mass and thereby, a lower stability limit.

Figure 2.5: Determination of added mass coefficient^[53]

Unlike added mass which influences the stability limit, added damping influences the stability of the system via the damping ratio ($\zeta = (c_s + c_a)/c_{crit} = (c_s + c_a)/2\sqrt{k_s m_s}$) for the same stability limit. Self-excited vibrations occur when the sum of the structural damping and the added damping is negative.^[19] It is also important to evaluate the damping of the system appropriately when calculating the forced vibration response of systems with positive total damping, where self-excited vibrations do not arise.^[19]

Several analytical expressions can be found in literature for added damping depending on the chosen setting of quiescent fluid, cross-flow, parallel flow and two-phase flow.^{[19],[22]} For single phase cross flow, in particular, the damping ratio in both longitudinal direction x and transverse direction y is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_x &= \frac{1}{4\pi} V_r \frac{\rho d^2}{m} C_D \\ \zeta_y &= \frac{1}{8\pi} V_r \frac{\rho d^2}{m} C_D \\ V_r &= \frac{U}{f_n d}\end{aligned}\tag{2.11}$$

This reveals an inverse dependence on the mass ratio. The damping is also noticed to be half in the lift direction compared to the axial direction. It is thus expected that transverse vibration will be larger compared to that in the longitudinal direction. Although a proportionality is seen with flow velocity, realizing that C_D is also a function flow velocity makes the relation non-linear in U and thus further comments are not made.

2.4. Conclusion

In this chapter, the most destructive mechanism of FIV occurring at high flow velocity has been reviewed. The mechanisms of FEI have been introduced which come into play based on the mass-damping parameter. The stability of a system under the influence of FEI is given by the critical velocity which is connected with the mass-damping parameter via the Connors' equation and its variations. Realizing that the mass ratio and damping needs to be considered separately, other models have been considered. In particular for cross flows, the unsteady models by Tanaka and Takahara^{[39],[50]} and Chen^[51] could be used while obtaining the unsteady fluid force coefficient data from a CFD simulation.

For any FSI system, it is important to account for the added mass and damping as it is influential in determining its stability. For tube arrays, care has to be taken for the array geometry and configuration for determining the added mass coefficient.

3

Vortex Induced Vibration

Vortex Induced Vibration (VIV) is the earliest known mechanism of FIV. In fact, many FEI cases were thought to be due to VIV. It was only in 1980, where the work of Païdoussis^[23], which reanalyzed practical experiences, pointed out the true culprit as FEI. However, VIV is just as troublesome when it comes to damaging things in a nuclear reactor.

Since ancient times, the existence of vortex shedding is known. Leonardo da Vinci sketched a row of vortices in the wake of a piling in a stream.^[54] This is shown in Figure 3.1. In 1878, Strouhal found that the Aeolian tones generated by a wire in the wind were proportional to the wind speed divided by the wire thickness. He also observed resonance when the natural tones matched with the aeolian tones. In 1879, Lord Rayleigh observed dominant vibrations of a violin string in the transverse direction compared to the longitudinal direction. The vorticity of the wake of a cylinder was associated with vortex formation by Benard in 1908, and with the formation of a stable street of staggered vortices by von Karman in 1912.^[22]

Figure 3.1: Sketch by Leonardo da Vinci: Obstacle creating turbulent wake^[55]

3.1. Mechanism of VIV

To understand VIV, it is best to grasp the concept of vortex shedding. Consider a single cylinder subjected to cross flow. As a fluid particle flows toward the leading edge of a cylinder, the pressure in the fluid particle rises from the free stream pressure to the stagnation pressure. The high fluid pressure near the leading edge impels flow about the cylinder as boundary layers develop about both sides. However, the high pressure is not sufficient to force the flow about the back of the cylinder at high Reynolds numbers. Near the widest section of the cylinder, the boundary layers separate from each side of the cylinder surface and form two shear layers that trail aft in the flow and bound the wake. Since the innermost portion of the shear layers, which is in contact with the cylinder, moves much more slowly than the outermost portion of the shear layers, which is in contact with the free flow, the shear layers roll into the near wake, where they fold on each other and coalesce into discrete swirling vortices.^{[22],[56],[57]} These vortices interact with the cylinder and are the source of the effects called VIV.

For multi-cylinder arrangements, the cause of vibration is seldom only vortex induced. A typical example is the work of Zdravkovich^[58] for two cylinders. He identified 3 regions of positioning a secondary cylinder behind and beside a primary cylinder which influence the response of both cylinders. These are the *proximity interference region* (can be interpreted as strictly FEI), *wake interference region* (can be interpreted as strictly VIV) and a *mixed region* of wake and proximity interference. This is shown in Figure 3.2. The influence of position of the second cylinder and flow velocity is made clear in his work.

Figure 3.2: Cylinder interaction regimes^[58]

3.2. Important Parameters influencing VIV

In order to understand VIV, it is imperative to look at the non-dimensional parameters that influence the flow behaviour around objects prone to VIV. The most important ones are the Reynolds Number (Re) and the Strouhal Number (St).

3.2.1. Reynolds Number

Vortex shedding is primarily governed by the Reynolds number, Re , which is defined by

$$Re = \frac{UD}{\nu} \quad (3.1)$$

where U is the freestream velocity, D is the characteristic length (diameter of a cylinder for example) and ν is the kinematic viscosity. The major Reynolds Number regimes of vortex shedding from a smooth circular cylinder is shown in Figure 3.3.

For very low Reynolds numbers ($Re < 5$), the flow remains attached to the cylinder. This regime where the viscous forces dominate the inertial forces is also called *Stokes flow*.^[59] For $5 < Re < 40$, the flow separates from both sides of the cylinder. The two vortices at both sides can be considered symmetric and stable. In the next flow regime, $40 < Re < 150$, the wake becomes unstable and the vortices are shed alternately from the cylindrical body. In this regime, the vortex street is still laminar. Between $150 < Re < 300$ the flow transitions to turbulent in the vortex wake. From $300 < Re < 1.5 \times 10^5$, the vortex street has become fully turbulent with the boundary layer still being laminar. This range is also called the *subcritical range* where the boundary layer remains fully laminar and the drag coefficient is nearly constant as can be seen from Figure 3.4.

In the *transitional range* from $1.5 \times 10^5 < Re < 3 \times 10^6$, the cylinder boundary layer becomes turbulent and the separation point moves to an aft position. The formation of laminar separation bubbles result in an overall reduction in drag, also called *drag crisis*, as can be seen from Figure 3.4. This flow regime is highly sensitive to inflow turbulence and surface roughness, therefore measurements of C_D are more scattered in this region. Here, the regular shedding process is disrupted and the spectrum of shedding frequencies is broadened for smooth surface cylinders.

Figure 3.3: Regimes of fluid flow across smooth circular cylinders^[60]

Figure 3.4: Experimental Measurements of Drag variation with Re ^[61]

The range of $Re > 3 \times 10^6$ is the *supercritical regime*. Laminar separations are no longer formed and the flow transitions to turbulence without separating. The flow remains attached longer and so has higher skin friction. Correspondingly, the drag rises from the dip in the *drag crisis* as can be seen from [Figure 3.4](#). Here, the turbulent vortex shedding is re-established.

3.2.2. Strouhal Number

The Strouhal Number, St , is the dimensionless proportionality constant between the predominant frequency of vortex shedding, f_s , and the free stream velocity, U , divided by the cylinder width, D , and is given by

$$f_s = \frac{StU}{D} \tag{3.2}$$

For cylinders inclined to the flow, it was found that the shedding frequency varies as^{[62],[63]}

$$f_s(\theta) = f_s(\theta = 0) \cos\theta \tag{3.3}$$

where θ is the angle of inclination of the cylinder axis from being perpendicular to the flow and is valid upto $\theta = 30^\circ$. At larger angles, end effects become increasingly important. As a consequence of the geometry of the vortex street, oscillations in lift occur at the shedding frequency but oscillations in the drag force occur at twice the shedding frequency.

The Strouhal number of a stationary circular cylinder in a subsonic flow is a function of Reynolds number and, to a lesser extent, surface roughness and free stream turbulence, as shown in [Figure 3.5](#). In particular, the effect of surface roughness is pronounced in the transitional regime, where very smooth surface cylinders have a chaotic, disorganized, high-frequency wake and Strouhal numbers as high as 0.5, while rough surface cylinders have organized, periodic wakes with Strouhal numbers of $St = 0.25$. In general, a Strouhal number of $St = 0.21$ is assumed for single cylinders in cross-flow.

Figure 3.5: Variation of Strouhal Number with Reynolds Number^[22]

However, the same does not hold for multi-cylinder configurations. The array configuration and geometry significantly affect the vortex shedding and thereby the Strouhal Number. In particular, for two cylinder in-line configurations, if the second cylinder is placed further away from the first cylinder, the two cylinders shed their own unique vortices. On the other hand, for small cylinder gaps, the two cylinders behave like a single object and shed a single combined wake.^[58] For tube arrays, the side-by-side spacing also matters. The commonly used Strouhal map in heat exchanger design, as given by Fitzhugh,^[64] is shown in Figure 3.6. Note that the Strouhal Number quoted here uses the gap velocity rather than the freestream velocity. Although commonly used, it has yet to distinguish the acoustic component in the result and is based on stationary cylinders. So, these charts are to be used with caution and are at best indicative.

Figure 3.6: Fitzhugh Strouhal map^[64]

The discussion so far may give the reader a misconception that vortex shedding is a steady, harmonic, two-dimensional process. This is quite far from the truth. Vortex shedding from a stationary cylinder in the higher Reynolds number range does not occur at a single distinct frequency, but rather it wanders over a narrow band of frequencies with a range of amplitudes and it is not constant along the span. The three-dimensionality of vortex shedding can be characterized by a spanwise correlation length. This correlation length, expressed as multiples of diameter, decreases with increasing Re .^[22]

3.2.3. Other Influencing Parameters

Besides the Reynolds number and the Strouhal number, there are other influencing parameters that impact VIV as well. In Figure 3.7 all the influence parameters are illustrated, as they were brought together by Zdravkovich^[65]. The other influence parameters illustrated in Figure 3.7 tend to have a smaller effect on VIV than the Reynolds number or Strouhal number, except for the cylinder oscillations. More details about the effect of cylinder oscillations are provided in the following sub-section. Besides the smaller effect of most of the influencing parameters, their effects have also been investigated at high Reynolds numbers. The interested reader is referred, for example, to studies of Barnett & Cermack^[66] and Achenbach & Heinecke,^[67] which addressed the surface roughness and free stream turbulence at supercritical Reynolds numbers, respectively.

Figure 3.7: Typical disturbances that have an impact on VIV^[65]

3.2.4. Effect of Cylinder Motion on Wake

As mentioned in the previous sub-section, the motion of the cylinder has an influence on the vortex shedding and thereby on VIV. A distinction between in-line oscillations and transverse oscillations has been made (in reality, both occur at the same time). The study of Sarpkaya^[68] found similar response branches for a 2-DoF experiment as in transverse 1-DoF studies. It was concluded that 2-DoF XY motion studies do not lead to significant variations in maximum resonant amplitudes compared to Y-only studies. Under the conditions when natural frequency is equal in both directions, it was shown by Sarpkaya^[68] that the response amplitude is 20% larger and the critical velocity range is also 20% larger. It was reasoned that the transverse oscillations were the main driver of the response amplitude and the critical wind speed range. The focus is thus brought to transverse vibrations.

According to Blevins,^[22] there are five main effects of the transverse cylinder motion on the wake. These are

1. The strength of the shed vortices increases.
2. The spanwise correlation of the wake increases.
3. The vortex shedding frequency can shift to the frequency of cylinder vibration leading to *lock-in* or high amplitude vibrations.
4. The mean drag of the cylinder increases.
5. The phase, sequence, and pattern of vortices in the wake can be altered.

The most crucial effects are the alteration of the wake and the lock-in phenomena which relate to the other prescribed effects of cylinder motion. In particular, differences were observed between free vibration and forced vibration. In the critical work by Williamson & Roshko^[57], 2S ('S' for single) and 2P ('P' for pair) vortex modes of the wake were discovered for free vibration. On the other hand, for forced vibration, an additional P+S mode was discovered in many experimental studies.^{[57],[69]–[71]} These modes are shown in a vortex wake mode map given in Figure 3.8. In the earliest works, such as those by Bishop & Hassan^[72] and Feng^[73], a jump in phase of transverse force was observed. This was attributed to a change from 2S to 2P mode by Williamson & Roshko^[57] and was experimentally confirmed by Brika & Laneville.^{[74],[75]}

Figure 3.8: Map of regimes for vortex wake modes^[57]

The response of a cylinder in VIV has been found to be greatly influenced by the mass ratio ($m^* = \frac{m}{\frac{\pi}{4}\rho D^2}$) and mass-damping ($m^*\zeta$) parameter. The early works, such as those by Feng^[73], were done using air and thus a high mass ratio of $m^* = 248$. In a later work by Khalak & Williamson^[76] who used water and thereby a low mass ratio of $m^* = 2.4$, a starkly different response with increasing reduced velocity was observed. This is shown in Figure 3.9. Note that the flow velocity has been non-dimensionalized as $U^* = \frac{U}{f_N D}$, vibrational frequency as $f^* = \frac{f_{obj}}{f_N}$ and maximum amplitude as $A_{max}^* = \frac{y_{max}}{D}$. In some literature, flow velocity is also represented by the reduced velocity, $U_R = \frac{U}{f_s D}$.

Figure 3.9: Comparison of response of low vs high mass-damping^[77]

Quite some differences are observed from the above figure. In particular, the definition of resonance or lock-in is challenged. The earlier definition of resonance was defined as that range of frequency when the vibrational frequency of the object matches with the natural frequency, i.e $f^* = 1$.^{[22],[78]} This definition was observed to be true for high mass-damping parameter. As we see from Figure 3.9b, for low mass-damping, the value of f^* for the lock-in regime lies at about 1.4. Thus the definition of the condition for resonance was redefined by Sarpkaya^[68] to the match in the shedding frequency, f_s and the vibrational frequency of the object, f_{obj} .

Another observation is the existence of different branches in the response curve shown in Figure 3.9a. For the high mass-damping, the curve by Feng^[73] shows an ‘initial branch’ and a ‘lower branch’. However, for the low mass-damping, an ‘upper branch’ is also observed. Furthermore, the range of synchronization or the lock-in regime appears to be larger for the low mass-damping parameter.

Consider the switch in the timing of vortex shedding described by Zdravkovich^[79] and Williamson & Roshko^[57] when the amplitude jumps from the initial to lower branch in high mass-damping cases such as Feng.^[73] In contrast, for low mass and damping, there are two mode jumps, and it is not immediately clear which one corresponds to the switch in vortex shedding timing. To shed light on this question, Govardhan & Williamson^[80] considered the “total” fluid force, as well as the “vortex” force. The basis of the theory came from Lighthill^{[81],[82]} who showed that the total fluid force (F_{TOTAL}) can be split into a “potential force” component $F_{POTENTIAL}$, given in this case by the potential added mass force, and a “vortex force” component (F_{VORTEX}) that is due only to the dynamics of all the shed vorticity. Govardhan & Williamson^[80] set out to deduce what the vortex force is from direct experimental measurement of the total fluid force. They also defined corresponding phase differences ϕ_{VORTEX} and ϕ_{TOTAL} . Their result is shown in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.10: Overview of the low mass-damping response^[80]

From their work, it was concluded that while traversing from the initial branch to the upper branch, a jump in vortex phase occurs and thereby a jump from 2S to 2P mode of shedding. On the other hand, while traversing from the upper branch to the lower branch, a jump in the total phase occurs which is not associated with switch in the time of shedding contrasting to Zdravkovich’s^[79] claim for high mass-damping case.

As mentioned earlier, lowering the mass ratio (m^*) in particular seems to increase the extent of synchronization regime. It could be conjectured that as $m^* \rightarrow 0$, the extent of synchronization should tend to infinity. In reality, there exists a finite critical mass ratio, m^*_{CRIT} , below which synchronization regime becomes infinitely wide. In 1999, Khalak & Williamson^[83] had provided an expression for the variation of f^* with m^* for high mass-damping. This was given as

$$f^* = \sqrt{\frac{m^* + C_A}{m^* + C_{EA}}} \quad (3.4)$$

where C_A is the potential added mass coefficient (usually taken as 1) and C_{EA} is the effective added mass coefficient. Govardhan & Williamson^[80] provided a similar expression for the lower branch for a low mass-damping response given as

$$f^*_{LOWER} = \sqrt{\frac{m^* + 1}{m^* - 0.54}} \quad (3.5)$$

They thus quoted a critical mass ratio of $m_{CRIT}^* = 0.54 \pm 0.02$. This unique critical mass ratio is valid for $(m^* + C_A)\zeta < 0.05$. Figure 3.11 shows the existence of a critical mass ratio. It also shows that for low amplitude vibrations, if the mass ratio is reduced below the critical value, large amplitude oscillations can set in.

Figure 3.11: Discovery of a critical mass^[84]

With the realization of the effect of mass-damping on the response, the next step in research was to obtain an expression using the mass-damping parameter that could potentially collapse all A_{max}^* data in a single plot. The use of mass-damping parameter was based on several studies.^{[84],[85]} A parameter was independently derived from a response analysis involving the van der Pol equation by Skop & Griffin,^[86] and they compiled data from several different experiments as a means to usefully predict response amplitudes. The combined response parameter was subsequently termed S_G in Skop,^[87] and is defined as

$$S_G = 2\pi^3 St^2 (m^* \zeta) \tag{3.6}$$

Griffin^[88] made the first extensive compilations of several investigations using S_G and provided the famous Griffin plot as shown in Figure 3.12. Voices against the use of the plot were raised by Sarpkaya on several occasions.^{[68],[89]–[91]} He pointed out that the mass ratio and damping are independent and that the Griffin plot is valid only for $S_G > 1$. On the other hand, Griffin & Ramberg^[92] performed two sets of experiments, each for the same value of $S_G = 0.5–0.6$, but with dissimilar mass ratios, $m^* = 4.8$ and 43. The peak amplitude was found to be roughly unchanged with $A_{max}^* = 0.5$ despite $S_G < 1$.

Figure 3.12: The Griffin plot based on data collected by Skop & Balasubramanian^[93]

To add to this conundrum, using a linear scale as in Figure 3.12 rather than the traditional log-log plot, reveals large scatter in the data. The conclusion was made by Khalak & Williamson^[83] that it was unreasonable to collapse data for different VIV systems (free cylinder, cantilever, pivoted cylinders, etc.) onto a single plot. In particular, Khalak & Williamson^[83] provided a response vs mass ratio plot specifically for elastically mounted cylinders as shown in Figure 3.13. The collapse of data was found to be successful for $m^* > 2$ and $(m^* + C_A)\zeta > 0.006$. This translates to a valid Griffin plot regime down to about $S_G \sim 0.01$, far lower than the value quoted by Sarpkaya^[89] of about $S_G \sim 1$.

Figure 3.13: Griffin plot for elastically mounted cylinders based on data by Khalak & Williamson^[83]

There are several literature available that try to capture VIV response analytically for free and forced vibration. These have been categorized by Chen^[32] as

- Self-Excited Oscillation Models
 - *Lift or Wake Oscillator Model*: Lift coefficient is assumed to satisfy a van der Pol-type equation based on observation by Bishop & Hassan^[72]. This is the most frequently used type of model in literature.
 - *Birkhoff's Oscillation Model*: The added fluid region behind the cylinder is modeled as Birkhoff's oscillator by Funakawa^[94]. It is shown that flutter is possible in a limited range of flow velocity.
 - *Variable Vortex Wake Width Model*: The vortex-wake width depends on cylinder amplitude and vortex origin time.^[95] The model is able to reproduce a certain narrowing of the wake.
- Forced Vibration Models
 - *Correlation Model*: The excitation is associated with the fluctuating lift coefficient, which is considered a function of oscillation amplitude.
 - *Variable Phase Model*: Sarpkaya^[89] and Satubli^[96] use the measured values of the in-phase and out-of-phase fluctuating lift forces to calculate the response of the vibrating cylinder.

3.3. VIV of Multi-Cylinder Configurations

Depending on cylinder spacings, as well as other system parameters, vortex shedding may or may not exist in a cylinder array. Early studies on vibration of cylinder arrays proceeded on the assumption that vortex shedding was the dominant mechanism. Thus, the main objective was to determine the vortex shedding frequency and the Strouhal Number. Key reviews in this area are given by Païdoussis^[97] and Weaver & Fitzpatrick^[98].

While summarizing the research work on the existence of vortex shedding in tube arrays, Païdoussis^[97] stated that periodic vortex shedding or 'Strouhal periodicity' commonly appeared for the first rows provided the upstream turbulence had not suppressed it. The appearance of vortex shedding deep within arrays is found to be dependent on Re , array geometry, mechanical properties of the tubes and the amplitude of tube vibration.

In later research works, Weaver et. al.^[99] and Fitzpatrick et. al.^[100] observed the presence of vortex shedding, if not a flow periodicity, even deep within the arrays. In an interesting flow visualization study by Abd-Rabbo & Weaver^[101], the development of vortex shedding in arrays is observed similar to the classical vortex shedding behind a single cylinder. The Strouhal periodicity is observed in the closely placed staggered array configurations, which is reported to be absent in the in-line array configurations.

Further study on the in-line tube arrays by Ziada & Oengören^[102] and Ziada & Oengören^[103] has enhanced the understanding of the generation of VIV. The fluid flowing in lanes forms the jet like structures, while the wakes of the cylinders are confined. The vortex-shedding excitations are generated in the first row due to the jet instabilities and persist for couple of rows downstream. The tube pitch ratio and the upstream turbulence has a major impact on the vortex-shedding in the front rows as well as deep in the arrays.

The vortex shedding in the staggered (normal triangular) arrangement is studied in Polak & Weaver^[104] for various pitch ratios and Reynolds numbers. In a comprehensive work by Ziada^[105] the vortex-shedding is shown to be generated by either jet, wake or shear layer instabilities, depending on the tube spacing, upstream turbulence, Reynolds number and the array configuration. Figure 3.14 shows the vortex shedding patterns in a staggered and in-line tube array. The sub-figures of Figure 3.14a show the influence of increasing Re on the flow vorticity. The closely spaced in-line configuration shown in Figure 3.14b shows the shear layer instabilities as the source of Strouhal periodicities.

Figure 3.14: Vortex shedding in tube arrays^[105]

3.3.1. Two-Cylinder Configurations

Pioneering work for two-cylinder configurations is done by Zdravkovich. He was able to identify a coupled region (proximity interference), a region of wake interference and a region of no interference. Besides classifying the regions, in his work^[58], he was able to observe different types of vortex shedding behaviour depending on the cylinder spacing in tandem (as P/D) and side-by-side (as T/D). This is shown in Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.15: Vortex shedding dependency on cylinder configuration^[58]

For in-line configurations, the measured Strouhal frequency with varying P/D is provided in Figure 3.16. In general, the vortex shedding frequencies behind the two cylinders are different. No distinct vortex shedding is found behind the upstream cylinders up to $P/D = 3.8$. For $P/D > 3.8$, the vortex shedding frequency reaches the value for an isolated cylinder. The vortex shedding exist in the whole range of spacing behind the downstream cylinder. It decreases with P/D for $1 < P/D < 3.8$, then jumps to higher values at $P/D \sim 3.8$, which is the same spacing at which the vortex shedding appears behind the upstream cylinder.

Figure 3.16: Variation of St with P/D ^[106]

A detailed study of two cylinders in tandem immersed in a water flow and spaced between 0.20 and 4 diameters was made by King & Johns^[107]. They found that complex mutual interactions can arise between the flow, vortex shedding, and the motion of the cylinders. The dynamic response of the cylinders is a function of pitch ratio, reduced flow velocity, mass ratio, and damping value. Reynolds number was also found to be of key importance: Re must exceed 1200-1500 for in-line oscillation to occur and must exceed 100 for cross-flow oscillation to occur. The responses, which depend strongly on P/D , have been summarized by Chen^[32] as follows:

- $P/D < 2.75$: Symmetric vortices are shed from both cylinders in the range $1.25 < U_R < 2.5$ and both cylinders oscillate in the in-line direction provided the mass-damping parameter is less than 2.4.
- $P/D > 2.75$: For $1.25 < U_R < 2.5$, the upstream cylinder oscillates inline and sheds symmetric vortices but the downstream cylinders do not oscillate and a wide turbulent wake is formed.
- $1.5 < P/D < 7$: For $2.7 < U_R < 3.8$, the alternate wake from the upstream cylinder generally reinforces that from the downstream cylinder.
- $1.25 < P/D < 7$: The alternate vortex shedding associated with the oscillating upstream cylinder generally reinforces that from the downstream cylinder.

Subsequent experimental work after King & Johns^[107] was given by Jendrzejczyk et. al.^[108] who carried out experiments for $P/D = 1.75$. The results for response and orbital paths are given in Figure 3.17 and Figure 3.18. There are two peaks in the response curves in the drag direction. The peaks correspond to the reduced flow velocities equal to 1.7 and 3.0, respectively. This is consistent with the experimental results by King & Johns^[107].

As the flow velocity increases, predominant cylinder motion changes from the drag direction to the lift direction. At large oscillations, the upstream cylinder vibrates more severely than the downstream one. The two cylinders vibrate out of phase when they execute large oscillations. The orbital paths bend in the downstream direction. This can be attributed to the drag variation—that is, when the cylinders are farthest from the equilibrium position, the drag force acting on the cylinders becomes larger.

Figure 3.17: Tube displacement components for two tubes in tandem^[108]

Figure 3.18: Tube orbital paths for two tubes in tandem^[108]

3.4. Conclusion

In this chapter, the earliest known mechanism of FIV is reviewed. This mechanism comes in to play in a range of reduced velocities where the vortex shedding frequency latches onto the vibrational frequency of the object. The Reynolds number, Strouhal number and the mass-damping of the system greatly influence the response. Furthermore, for tube arrays, the array geometry and configuration has an equally important role to play. For in-line two cylinder arrays, the importance of P/D is highlighted along with the change from a low amplitude in-line vibration to a high amplitude transverse vibration with increasing flow velocity.

4

Acoustic Resonance

Acoustic resonance is of high relevance in heat exchangers such as gas heaters and boilers containing tube bundles.^[19] Acoustic resonance is found to occur in conjunction with VIV where the shedding frequency matches with one of the acoustic natural frequencies of the acoustic cavity encompassing the tube bundle. This phenomena occurs for both gas and liquid flows. However, the speed of sound in liquid is much higher than that in gas, thereby the acoustic natural frequency is much higher for liquids compared to gas and is thus of concern in practical applications at high reduced velocities. For gas flows, acoustic resonance depends on tube bundle geometry, gas flow normal to tube axes and the acoustic space limited by duct or vessel walls.^[19]

Figure 4.1: Overview of acoustic resonance in tube bundle^[19]

4.1. Mechanism of Acoustic Resonance

When the gas flow rate in the duct (or vessel) surpasses a critical level, generation of high-level noise (even upto 120-150dB) by acoustic resonance may occur. This may even lead to structural damage. With increasing flow velocity, the frequency of shedding increases following from the constant Strouhal relationship where the gap velocity is taken to define the Strouhal number. This at some point reaches the natural frequency f of an acoustic mode i in the duct given by

$$f_i = \frac{ic}{2W}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (4.1)$$

where c is the speed of sound and W is the width of the duct. The acoustic resonance is a self-excited phenomenon. Vortices shed from the tube bundle excite an acoustic mode. The resulting regular acoustic pressure fluctuations caused by this mode in turn promote and strengthen the synchronization of vortex shedding which thereby increases the net excitation energy of the acoustic mode.^[19] Acoustic resonance is established when the following conditions are satisfied:^[19]

1. *Frequency Condition:* vortex shedding frequency matches with the natural frequency of any acoustic mode in the duct.
2. *Energy Condition:* energy supplied by vortex shedding to an acoustic mode exceeds the energy dissipation of this mode in the acoustic field.

4.2. Classification of Acoustic Resonance

Acoustic resonances can be classified into two broad types depending on the acoustic mode shape as shown in Figure 4.2. These are:^[19]

1. *Transverse Mode*: The acoustic resonant modes are dominant in the direction perpendicular to both the gas flow and tube axes. This is more commonly encountered than the other type. It is further classified based on the location of resonance in the tube bundle:
 - (a) The main part of the resonance exists within the tube bundle.
 - (b) The resonance occurs mainly in the cavity between upstream and downstream tube bundles.
2. *Longitudinal Mode*: The acoustic modes parallel to the gas flow direction are dominant. The trick of using baffle plates, although works for transverse mode, does not suppress longitudinal mode of acoustic resonance. Using bell-mouths at the end of the duct or fins in front of the tubes do well in delaying longitudinal acoustic resonance.

Figure 4.2: Classification of acoustic resonance by mode shape: (a) transverse mode, and (b) longitudinal mode^[19]

4.3. Strouhal Number

The Strouhal Number has already been introduced in the discussion for VIV having the expression $St = f_s D / U$ with the flow velocity taken as the free stream for single cylinder and gap velocity for tube arrays. For acoustic resonance, other variations of the Strouhal number exist. For tube-banks, the Strouhal number in a given range of Re is mainly dependent on the array geometry. Such a dependency was already introduced with the Fitzhugh^[64] Strouhal map that uses the standard definition of Strouhal number. Owen^[109] gives the expression as

$$St_O = \frac{1}{2(P/D)} \quad (4.2)$$

and the expanded formulation of Bryce et. al.^[110] is given by

$$St_B = \frac{1}{2(P/D) - 1} \quad (4.3)$$

While the Fitzhugh-Strouhal numbers, which are based on a review of all previous data are known to represent closely the vortex-shedding theory, the Strouhal numbers given in Equation 4.2 and Equation 4.3 are more representative of the turbulent or turbulent-buffeting theory of excitation.^[111] More details about turbulence induced vibrations are provided in the next chapter.

The Strouhal number, St_{ai} , extracted by Eisinger et. al.^[111] from experimental results of acoustically vibrating cases (acoustic Strouhal number) is given by

$$St_{ai} = \frac{f_i D}{v_i} \quad (4.4)$$

where f , is the frequency of the acoustic (standing wave) vibration in the i^{th} mode, and v_i is the flow gap velocity at the onset of the vibration.

Figure 4.3 gives a comparison of three Strouhal numbers with the acoustic Strouhal number for 27 vibrating tube banks. It can be seen that the Fitzhugh-Strouhal numbers closely follow the acoustic values.

Figure 4.3: Comparison of Strouhal numbers for vibrating cases^[111]

4.4. Acoustic Vibration Criteria

Several acoustic resonance criteria have been provided in literature. A comparative analysis was carried out by Eisinger et. al.^[111] in his review. The following main criteria have been introduced and compared:

The Grotz & Arnold Criterion^[112]

The criterion is given by the expression

$$\Gamma = \frac{W/D}{(P/D - 1)i} \quad (4.5)$$

where Γ is the Grotz and Arnold dimensionless number, W is the width (transverse dimension) of the flow channel perpendicular to tube axes, D is the tube diameter, and i is the mode number of the transverse standing wave. According to this criterion, strong acoustic vibration is likely for $\Gamma < 62 - 80$ depending on the definition chosen for the Strouhal number. In all cases, 3 regions were identified: a region of certain vibration, a region of no vibration and a mixed region. This is clearly seen in Figure 4.4a plotted using the Fitzhugh-Strouhal number.

The Chen Criterion^{[113],[114]}

The Chen^[113] and the Chen & Young^[114] criterion is given by

$$\Psi = \frac{Re}{St} \left(1 - \frac{1}{P/D}\right)^2 \frac{1}{T/D} \quad (4.6)$$

where Ψ is the Chen dimensionless number, Re is the Reynolds number, and P/D , T/D , are the longitudinal and transverse tube spacing ratios, respectively. An alternative expression for the Chen number can be used which is given by

$$\Psi = \frac{Re}{He} M \left(1 - \frac{1}{P/D}\right)^2 \frac{1}{T/D} \quad (4.7)$$

where He is the Helmholtz number given by $He = Stv/c$ and M is the Mach number given by $M = v/c$. In his earlier work, Chen^[113] had prescribed a stability boundary of $\Psi = 600$ but this worked only for Wind Tunnels. Chen & Young^[114] later provided a practical stability boundary of $\Psi = 2000$. Just like Grotz and Arnold, 3 regions were identified. This is clearly seen in Figure 4.4b plotted using the Fitzhugh-Strouhal number.

Figure 4.4: Stability diagrams compiled based on the work of different authors by Eisinger et. al.^[111] (Note: Here, $x_l = P/D$ and $x_t = T/D$)

The Fitzpatrick Criteria^{[115],[116]}

Two formulations were presented:

- Fitzpatrick 1^[115]:

$$\Delta = \frac{\sqrt{Re}}{MSt} \frac{1}{2(P/D - 1)} \quad (4.8)$$

- Fitzpatrick 2^[116]:

$$\Delta^* = \frac{\sqrt{Re}}{MSt} \frac{1}{2(P/D - 1)T/D} \quad (4.9)$$

Here too, the same 3 regions were identified. This is clearly seen in [Figure 4.4c](#) and [Figure 4.4d](#) plotted using the Fitzhugh-Strouhal number. However, Eisinger et. al.^[111] remarked that there was quite some scatter in their data thus giving no clear boundaries to regions which would separate the vibratory from the non-vibratory cases.

Ziada et. al. Criterion^[117]

The Ziada parameter for in-line tube banks is given by

$$G_i = \sqrt{Re} \frac{P}{D} \frac{\nu}{cD} \quad (4.10)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity of the flowing gas. Ziada et. al.^[117] showed in a graphical presentation $(P/D)^2$ versus G_i , two regions separated by a curved line indicating the fields containing the vibrating and non-vibrating cases. This is clearly seen in [Figure 4.4e](#) plotted using the Fitzhugh-Strouhal number.

Blevins' Acoustic Vibration Map

Blevins & Bressler^[118] provided a map of P/D vs T/D on which 5 modes for the non-vibrating and 4 modes for the vibrating cases were shown. This is shown in [Figure 4.4f](#) that is plotted using the Fitzhugh-Strouhal number for non-vibrating case and Acoustic Strouhal number for vibrating case. The map showed that:

- For $P/D > 2.2$, acoustic vibration occurred in all cases.
- For $T/D > 2.8$ and $P/D \leq 2$, no vibration occurred.
- For $P/D < 2.3$ and $T/D \leq 2.8$, the region is mixed.

The main take-aways from the review of Eisinger et. al.^[111] are:

- Fitzhugh-Strouhal numbers closely match the acoustic Strouhal numbers extracted from the vibrating cases and thus seem best to represent the tube bank resonant behavior.
- The Chen criterion gave the best results in separating the vibrating from the non-vibrating cases.
- The Grotz & Arnold criterion separates the vibrating and the non-vibrating cases with much less certainty given its wide range of mixed cases.
- The Fitzpatrick as well as the Ziada et al. criteria show a significant shift in the positions of the individual regions relative to the original predictions and also fail to separate clearly a large number of cases.
- The cases from Eisinger et. al. superimposed upon the Blevins chart do not give a clear basis for separating the vibratory from the non-vibratory conditions.

4.5. Conclusion

In this section, the mechanism of FIV most connected with VIV has been reviewed. The mechanism and classification of acoustic resonance was provided. With the introduction of different variations of the Strouhal number, the different acoustic vibration criteria for transverse mode have been discussed. It was concluded that the Chen criteria based on the Fitzhugh-Strouhal number is the most accurate. However, this mechanism of FIV is more important for gas flows and holds less value for nuclear power plants that concerns itself with liquid flow where the flow velocities of interest are far lower than those required for acoustic resonance. Regardless, the reader is now aware of such a possibility and the need for special stability criteria.

5

Turbulence Induced Vibration

Turbulence Induced Vibration (TIV) or Turbulence Buffeting is felt to be a ‘background’ mechanism given that it is caused by the ever-present turbulence in the flow. It is the leading mechanism causing failure in axial flows. For cross-flows, it is an additive to other mechanisms such as VIV. Turbulence, in a very literal sense, means chaotic or random behaviour or in other words unpredictable in nature. But there is some order to this chaos. Involvement of statistics has improved the understanding of turbulence. Figure 5.1 shows that the Reynolds number involved in these flows are very different from each other raising an expectation of a very different flow pattern. However, looking at the wake region of these objects, it can clearly be seen that there are similarities between the flows.

(a) Flat Plate subjected to $Re = 4300$

(b) Grounded Tankship subjected to $Re = 10^7$

Figure 5.1: Large scale wake similarity observed for different objects at 45° angle of attack^[119]

5.1. Mechanism of TIV

To have a better understanding of TIV, consider an ideal cross-flow. Here, standard vortex shedding would dictate that we should observe periodic lift and drag forces as the excitation forces at a single frequency. However, in a real cross-flow that has a certain turbulence level, the frequency spectra of lift and drag would contain two components. The first would be a narrow band of frequencies due to organized vortex shedding. The second would be a wide band of frequencies, predominantly below f_s , due to flow turbulence in the incoming flow stream and in the wake. This is clearly shown in Figure 5.2.

The turbulence present in the flow that causes TIV could be generated locally by the fluid as it flows around the structure. This is termed as *near-field excitation*. On the other hand, turbulence could also be generated by upstream components such as inlet nozzles, elbows, etc. This is termed as *far-field excitation*.^[18]

Figure 5.2: Response spectrum of a tube in 1.5 pitch ratio rotated square array with water cross flow^[120]

The presence of turbulence in flow has an effect on fluid forces. These were given by Mulcahy^[121] and have been aptly summarized by Chen^[32]:

- The Reynolds number at which the boundary layer undergoes transition from laminar to turbulent flow is reduced. This is confirmed by the sharp decline in drag as well as increase in Strouhal number as shown in Figure 5.3.
- Degradation of 2D vortex shedding process for subcritical Re occurs, as measured by broadening and reduction in amplitude of vortex shedding peak in the lift force spectral density.
- Pressure fluctuations are created by the impinging turbulence. The associated random excitation forces are difficult to separate from those created by the wake.

The above-mentioned pressure fluctuations occur over the entire spectrum and the contribution of energy from the fluctuation at the natural frequency causes resonance and thereby TIV.

Figure 5.3: Effect of turbulence on flow^[122]

5.2. Predicting Structural Response to TIV

Like with FEI, TIV was misrepresented by VIV initially. Owen^[109] took the first step towards recognizing TIV by questioning the presence of vortex shedding in confined arrays. The excitations were attributed to the range of turbulence frequencies and a dominant frequency from the range. By measuring the velocity spectra in a tube array, he outlined a basis for a forced random vibration analysis.

Blevins^{[123],[124]} claimed that it is possible to provide an analytical solution to TIV if one assumes that (a) the fluid pressures are independent of the motion of the structure and (b) the fluid pressures are stationary in the sense that averages made over many cycles of oscillation are independent of the start of the averaging interval. With these assumptions, using the theory of random vibration, Blevins^[123] gave the expression of the mean of the squared response of the structure in a single mode as

$$\overline{Y^2} = \frac{CS_p(f_i)J}{f_i^3 \zeta_i m^2} \psi_i^2(z) \quad (5.1)$$

where m is the mass per unit length of the structure, f_i is the natural frequency for the i^{th} mode, ζ_i is the damping factor of the i^{th} mode and ψ_i is the mode shape. $S_p(f_i)$ is the turbulence spectrum at f_i and J represents the joint acceptance of the turbulence for the i^{th} mode. Joint acceptance is a measure of the efficiency of the pressure forces to excite a certain mode. C is a constant that depends on the definition of S_p and J . Two rational approaches to the random vibrations of structures have generally been employed in the literature. These are:^[124]

1. *Theory of Random Vibration*: This is to employ Equation 5.1 directly and then estimate the power spectra and joint acceptance of the turbulence to determine the mean square response. However, accurate estimates of power spectra and joint acceptance are rarely available for a particular system.
2. *Empirical Approach*: This is to by-pass the theory of random vibrations and empirically correlate observed vibration levels with known system parameters such as flow velocity and hydraulic diameter. However, this approach often neglects a parameter of fundamental importance, such as damping, and so can lead to erroneous results when applied to new systems.

Both approaches are also hampered by uncertainties in the nature of the turbulent forcing function, which, unlike vortex shedding, flutter, or whirling, depends on the details of upstream turbulence generators rather than the structure itself.^[124]

5.2.1. Tube Arrays in Cross-Flow

For tube arrays in cross-flow, TIV is usually seen as a secondary issue given that arrays are usually dominated by whirling instability. Two main theories for predicting the response of a tube array in cross flow are found in literature. These are the one by Pettigrew & Gorman^[125] and another by Blevins et. al.^[126] Both these theories rest on the following assumptions:^[98]

- There is no significant off-resonant tube response such as would be produced by a peak in the turbulence spectrum remote from the tube natural frequency.
- The turbulence is isotropic and perfectly correlated along the tube length.
- The power spectral density of the excitation force per unit length is proportional to the dynamic head.

Pettigrew & Gorman^[125] estimated that the required power spectra for use in Equation 5.1 to determine the mean square turbulence response is given by

$$S_p(f) = C_R^2 \left(\frac{\rho U^2 D}{2} \right)^2 \quad (5.2)$$

where C_R is different for upstream tubes and downstream tubes as shown in Figure 5.4. The joint acceptance is conservatively estimated as $J = 1$. This yields a mean square midspan response of a tube supported at both ends of

$$\frac{\overline{Y^2}}{D^2} = \frac{C_R^2}{16\pi^5} \left(\frac{U}{D} \right) \left(\frac{U}{fD} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\rho D^2}{m} \right)^2 \frac{1}{\zeta} \quad (5.3)$$

A random vibration theory was developed for the turbulence-induced in-line vibration by Blevins et. al.^[126] which differs from the Pettigrew theory only in the manner in which the pressure spectrum is estimated. By noting that the velocity spectra of turbulence inside a tube array have a characteristic humped appearance, as observed by Owen^[109], and a peak at the dominant frequency of vortex shedding, the pressure spectra was related to the velocity spectra by

$$S_p(f) = \rho^2 C_D^2 U^3 \left(\frac{\overline{u^2}}{U^2} \right) \left(\frac{D}{St} \right) G \left[\frac{fD}{StU} \right] \quad (5.4)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient of a tube based on the gap velocity U . $\overline{u^2}$ is the mean square turbulence velocity which has a typical value of $\sqrt{\overline{u^2}} = 0.2U$. $G[fD/(StU)]$ is a non-dimensional spectral shape which compares the tube natural frequency, f , with the dominant frequency of turbulence. The above spectra yield the following mean square response at midspan for a sinusoidal mode shape

$$\frac{\overline{Y^2}}{D^2} = \frac{C_D^2}{2^6 \pi^2 St} \left(\frac{U}{fD} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\rho D^2}{m} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\overline{u^2}}{U^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\zeta} \right) \left(\frac{L_c}{L} \right)^2 G\gamma \quad (5.5)$$

L_c is the spanwise correlation length, which is assumed to be much less than the tube length, L . γ is a mode shape factor and is approximately equal to 1. The plot of power spectral density is given in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.4: Random excitation coefficient C_R as a function of frequency^[97]

Figure 5.5: Power Spectral Density given as a lift coefficient^[97]

The above plots seem contradictory. Pettigrew theory gives us the expectation that upstream cylinders will vibrate more violently compared to the downstream cylinders while Blevins theory would have us expect the opposite. This difference could be attributed to the fact that Pettigrew & Gorman conducted their experiments in water while Blevins et. al. conducted them in air. The differences in upstream turbulence intensities is also suspected to have a role to play.^[97]

5.2.2. Tube Arrays in Axial Flow

In many heat exchanger designs, the mean flow is parallel to the tubes over the majority of the tube span. This is also true in nuclear applications such as steam generators and reactors. This parallel turbulent flow can induce vibrations that are of considerable practical importance. The theories of TIV of circular cylinders in a parallel turbulent flow can generally be placed in a power law form. For example, the prediction of Wambsganss and Chen with the modification by Blevins is given by^[98]

$$\frac{Y_{rms}}{D} = 0.036KD\sqrt{U} \left(\frac{\rho D^2}{m} \right) \left(\frac{U}{fD} \right)^{1.5} \left(\frac{d}{D} \right)^{1.5} \left(\frac{D}{L} \right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{1}{\zeta} \right)^{0.5} \sin \frac{\pi z}{L} \quad (5.6)$$

for a rod of diameter D with a sinusoidal spanwise mode shape, natural frequency f , mass per unit length, including added mass, m , and damping ζ , which is exposed to a flow of mean velocity U , density ρ , and hydraulic diameter d .

In general, the theories express the characteristic vibration amplitude Y in the form

$$Y = K\rho^i U^j d^k D^e m^m f^n \zeta^o \quad (5.7)$$

where i through o are dimensionless exponents whose values are given in Table 5.1 for various theories.

Theory	i	j	k	e	m	n	o
Basile et. al. ^[127]	0.25	1.5	0.5	-0.5	-0.25	-1	0
Burgreen et. al. ^[128]	0.385	2.3	1	0.77	-0.65	-2.6	0
Chen ^[129]	1	2	0	1	0	-2	0
Païdoussis ^[130]	0.8	2.4	0.8	0.8	-0.66	-2	0
Reavis ^[131]	1	1.5	0.4	1.5	-1	-1.5	-0.5
Wambsganss & Chen ^[132]	1	2	1.5	1.5	-1	-1.5	-0.5

Table 5.1: Comparison of exponents in theories of parallel flow TIV of cylindrical structures^[98]

It can be easily seen that the variations of the exponents in Table 5.1 will result in large differences in the predictions of the various theories. Païdoussis^[133] remarked that the best accuracy one can hope to achieve in the prediction of vibration with these theories is about one order of magnitude. Blevins^[98] remarked that since the turbulent forces in a parallel flow are largely dependent on upstream turbulence generators, improvements in the theoretical work are unlikely to yield substantial improvements in accuracy unless the theories are tied to a specific system whose turbulence level can be accurately identified.

5.3. Conclusion

In this chapter, an ever-present mechanism of vibration was reviewed. Although the amplitudes of vibration are considerably lower compared to other mechanisms of FIV, TIV is the main cause of failure in axial flow systems. As for cross flows, it adds upon the response of some other mechanism such as VIV over the entire spectra of frequencies. The analytical theories for predicting the responses have been reviewed as well as realizing the limitation of accurately identifying turbulence levels. The turbulence is modelled, generally, in simulations that concerns itself with a numerical approach. The following chapter provides greater details about how this is achieved.

6

Numerical Simulation

Every numerical simulation is based on a mathematical model that tries to describe the physics of the phenomenon being studied. When considering Fluid Structure Interaction, this involves the equation governing the fluid domain, the structural domain and the ways to couple them both. This chapter provides a consolidated overview of the equations governing fluid dynamics, its associated turbulence modelling, structural dynamics and the various techniques available to couple the two separate domains.

6.1. Frames of Reference

While observing any physical phenomenon, choosing an appropriate frame of reference can simplify the numerical analysis, making it easier to interpret. An example of this would be the choice made by the astronomer Copernicus to analyze the trajectories of the planets keeping the sun as the center instead of earth. This small change in frame of reference simplified the complicated motion of the planets to just ellipses. The two basic frames of reference typically used in continuum mechanics are the *Lagrangian* and the *Eulerian* approach. The point of view particularly suitable for FSI is the *Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian* (ALE) approach.

6.1.1. Lagrangian Approach

The frame of reference is fixed to the material domain in this approach. The frame of reference moves according to the movement or deformation of the domain as shown in Figure 6.1. As can be seen in Figure 6.1a, the mesh points (dashed circles) move according to the movement of the material points (filled circles). This approach is often used in structural mechanics as it allows implicit treatment of moving boundaries and defines a property history to each material point.

6.1.2. Eulerian Approach

In the Eulerian approach the frame of reference is fixed to a particular spatial location regardless of the movement of the material being observed as shown in Figure 6.1b. Thus to measure the change in any given property f over time at a given location x , one must add the change of the property at that location with time and the convective transport of neighboring material to that location with a material velocity U . This change is often taken care by the material derivative,

$$\frac{Df}{Dt} = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + (U \cdot \nabla)f \quad (6.1)$$

Given that it can handle any arbitrary deformation, it is quite popularly used in fluid dynamics.

6.1.3. Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian Approach

The Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) approach allows to move the frame of reference independent of the material motion. Figure 6.1c depicts the motion of the frame of reference with this approach. This method brings together the best of both the aforementioned approaches by following the motion of the material at the fluid structure interface in a Lagrangian way, while the computational mesh in the interior can be moved arbitrarily to optimize the shape of the elements. In this frame of reference, the velocity in the governing equations becomes relative to the deforming mesh.

Figure 6.1: Lagrangian, Eulerian and ALE frames of reference shown with 1-D computation grid (dashed circles), material points (filled circles) and material domain (grey lines)^[134]

6.2. Governing Equations

The first step towards solving any problem numerically is to determine the set of equations governing the phenomena being studied. This section shows the governing equations for both the fluid domain and the structural domain.

6.2.1. Fluid Domain

The field of fluid dynamics is categorized by types of flow, which also change the behaviour of the governing equations. These categories of flow are compressible or incompressible flow, viscous or inviscid flow and laminar or turbulent flow. The flow is considered incompressible if the density of the respective fluid is constant within an infinitesimal volume which is the case when the speed of sound is large compared to the velocity of the fluid (corresponding to Mach number less than 0.3). Viscosity of the fluid determines its rate of deformation given a certain amount of shear. Inviscid flows are characterized by low viscosity and nearly negligible shear forces. Turbulent flows are characterized by highly irregular flow patterns in space and time, that occur when several flow parameters (summarized by the Reynolds Number) exceed a certain threshold.

6.2.1.1. Conservation of Mass

Conservation of mass states that the total mass of fluid in a closed system is constant over time and results in the continuity equation,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \rho(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U}) + (\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla)\rho \quad (6.2)$$

where \mathbf{U} is the velocity vector and ρ is the density of the fluid. For an incompressible fluid flow, the partial derivative of ρ w.r.t time and space vanish. Hence, the above can be written as

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0 \quad (6.3)$$

6.2.1.2. Conservation of Momentum

The conservation of momentum is a consequence of Newton's second law stating that the change in momentum of a system is due to an external force \mathbf{F} acting on it. This above law can be written as,

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{U} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{F} \quad (6.4)$$

where p is the pressure field and τ is the viscous stress tensor which in turn can be written using the following constitutive law for Newtonian fluids

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_k} \right) \quad (6.5)$$

where μ is the viscosity of the fluid. For an incompressible flow, the last term of Equation 6.5 vanishes and the conservation of momentum can be written as

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{U} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{U} \right) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U} + \rho \mathbf{F} \quad (6.6)$$

The equations of conservation of mass and conservation of momentum for fluids are together called the *Navier-Stokes Equations* (NSE). The above derived equations are in Eulerian frame of reference. As the ALE approach is used in FSI problems, the NSE for incompressible flows is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} &= 0 \\ \rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{c} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{U} \right) &= -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{U} + \rho \mathbf{F} \end{aligned} \quad (6.7)$$

where \mathbf{c} is the convective velocity defined as $\mathbf{U} - \hat{\mathbf{U}}$, where \mathbf{U} is the material velocity w.r.t. the spatial domain and $\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ is the mesh velocity which is the velocity of the referential domain w.r.t the spatial domain.

6.2.2. Structural Domain

Most structural mechanics applications are limited to comparatively small strains due to the risk of material failure, e.g. cracks. Therefore, we deal with rather small displacements (compared to fluid dynamics), allowing the use of Lagrangian description of the kinematics. The deformation of an elastic, isotropic, homogeneous and incompressible structure is governed by the Saint-Venant-Kirchhoff material model which is derived using the conservation of momentum using Lagrangian point of view. The resulting equation in the differential form is^[135]

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^2} = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{S} + \rho \mathbf{f} \quad (6.8)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the displacement field, ρ is the solid density, \mathbf{f} consists of body forces and \mathbf{S} is the 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor which models surface forces.

6.3. Turbulence modelling

Due to the non-linearity of the NSE, arriving at an analytical result is very difficult, so much so that a prize money of a million-dollars awaits for the one who solves them. For now, the only known method to accurately and efficiently solve these equations for complex geometries and cases are by the use of numerical methods. Turbulent flows consist of different length and time scales that are continuously created and dissipated in an *energy cascade*. Computing all these scales is a numerical nightmare. Current state of the art take different approaches to numerically solve the NSE. These are *Direct Numerical Simulations* (DNS), *Large Eddy Simulations* (LES), *Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes* (RANS) and certain hybrid methods such as *Detached Eddy Simulations* (DES).

6.3.1. Direct Numerical Simulations

The DNS is a brute force solver that computes the NSE for all the scales involved in the flow. DNS demands extremely fine grids and time steps (right down to the *Kolmogorov scales*) and is therefore the most expensive and accurate technique. The solution comes out as an accurate unadulterated time history that is very attractive for turbulent flows. However, the limitations of computational power restrict the use of DNS in academic settings of low *Re* flows.

6.3.2. Large Eddy Simulations

The LES is a novel method that was first introduced by Smagorinsky^[136] in 1963. The idea here is to solve the NSE only for the largest of the eddies which the mesh grid can allow for, while the smaller scales are calculated using mathematical models. The order of this sub-grid filtering of these smaller scales is defined by the isotropy of the turbulence eddies. Although LES is computationally more efficient than DNS, the assumptions involved in Sub-Grid Scale (SGS) modelling require accuracy to be paid as a price. For nuclear applications whose domain could span over a few meters, LES is still computationally expensive to carry out.

6.3.3. Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes

RANS is an attractive, low cost method to solve the NSE for turbulent flows. Unlike LES and DNS, RANS models do not provide any data on the velocity or pressure fluctuations in the flow field, since they only calculate the average values of the same. To understand this, consider the continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (6.9)$$

The velocity $u_i(t)$ can be written as the sum of the mean \bar{u} (time averaged) and the fluctuations $u'_i(t)$ as

$$u_i = \bar{u} + u'_i \quad (6.10)$$

Substituting Equation 6.10 in Equation 6.9 and averaging the whole equation w.r.t time gives

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (6.11)$$

Similarly, the momentum equation for an incompressible, steady flow is given by

$$\frac{\partial u_i u_j}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[-\frac{p}{\rho} \delta_{ij} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] \quad (6.12)$$

Substituting Equation 6.10 in Equation 6.12 and averaging the whole equation w.r.t time gives

$$\frac{\partial \overline{u_i u_j}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[-\bar{p} \delta_{ij} - \overline{u'_i u'_j} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] \quad (6.13)$$

Collectively Equation 6.11 and Equation 6.13 are called the RANS equations. It is seen that unlike the normal NSE which had 4 equations and 4 unknowns, this particular set of equations has more unknowns than equations creating a *closure problem*. The extra equations are formulated by modelling the $-\overline{u'_i u'_j}$ term which when multiplied by ρ is called the *Reynolds Stress Tensor* denoted by τ_{ij} . One of the earliest models of the Reynolds Stress was provided by Boussinesq and is known as the *Boussinesq hypothesis*.^[137] Popular turbulence models such as the $k-\epsilon$, $k-\omega$ and Spalart Allmaras are all based on this hypothesis and are called *Eddy Viscosity Models* (EVM). There are other models which do not rely on the Boussinesq approximation. These are the *Reynolds Stress Models* (RSM).

6.3.3.1. Eddy Viscosity Models

The boussinesq approximation models the Reynolds Stress τ_{ij} as being proportional to the mean strain rate tensor S_{ij} and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{ij} &= 2\rho\nu_t S_{ij} - \frac{2}{3}\rho k \delta_{ij} \\ -\overline{u'_i u'_j} &= \nu_t \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \frac{2}{3}k \delta_{ij} \end{aligned} \quad (6.14)$$

where $k = \frac{1}{2} \overline{u'_k u'_k}$ is the turbulent kinetic energy and ν_t is the modelled *Eddy Viscosity*. The very first method to model the Eddy Viscosity was the Prandtl's mixing length hypothesis which proposed that the eddy viscosity is proportional to the product of square of the mixing length l_m and the velocity gradient in the wall normal direction giving^[137]

$$\nu_t = l_m^2 \left| \frac{\partial \bar{u}}{\partial y} \right| \quad (6.15)$$

This model is also known as the *Zero Equation Model*. But estimation of the mixing length is specific to the geometry and the type of flow thus making the simulation unreliable. Later, the *One Equation Model* of Spalart-Allmaras was made available which still had shortcomings. This paved the way for *Two Equation Models*. Jones & Launder^[138] provided the $k-\epsilon$ model. It uses iterative methods to converge to the solution for the turbulent kinetic energy k and the rate of turbulent kinetic energy dissipation ϵ . The eddy viscosity is then calculated using

$$\nu_t = C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\epsilon} \quad (6.16)$$

where, $C_\mu \approx 0.09$, is an adjustable constant depending on the case. The $k - \epsilon$ model is popular for high Reynolds number flows since it is robust. The downside of this model being that the prediction near the wall is not very good. This is usually compensated by usage of wall functions, which model the boundary layers. The $k - \omega$ model proposed by Wilcox^[139], is an improvement over the standard $k - \epsilon$ model since it does not require wall functions. However, this model is not stable for geometries with sudden changes in gradients, such as sudden separation. The concerned equations are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_t &= C_\omega \frac{k}{\omega} \\ \omega &= \frac{\epsilon}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (6.17)$$

There are other models which have been developed based on these two models like the $k - \epsilon$ RNG model and the $k - \omega$ SST model. These models try to eliminate a few of the problems that the standard models tend to face, making them more accurate. The main disadvantage of the EVM is that they assume turbulence to be isotropic in nature for all the length scales which is not true for many cases. Therefore, in many models it is observed that these models over predict the values of turbulent kinetic energy in many regions or they tend to stabilize the results for an unsteady turbulent case.

6.3.3.2. Reynolds Stress Model

Reynolds Stress Model (RSM) solves the closure problem without the Boussinesq hypothesis thereby overcoming the embedded assumption of isotropic turbulence. This model directly calculates the Reynolds stress from the transport equations and is thus expected to provide more accurate results compared to EVM. Proposed by Launder et. al.^[140] in 1975, this model involves calculating the Reynolds stress $\overline{\rho u'_i u'_j}$ from the transport equations given below.^[141]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\overline{\rho u'_i u'_j}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} (\rho u_k \overline{u'_i u'_j}) &= - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} [\overline{\rho u'_k u'_i u'_j} + \overline{p'(\delta_{kj} u'_i + \delta_{ik} u'_j)}] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left[\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \right] \\ &\quad - \rho \left(\overline{u'_i u'_k} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_k} + \overline{u'_j u'_k} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_k} \right) - \rho \beta (g_i \overline{u'_j \theta} + g_j \overline{u'_i \theta}) + p \left(\frac{\partial u'_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u'_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \\ &\quad - 2\mu \frac{\partial u'_i}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial u'_j}{\partial x_k} - \rho \Omega_k (\overline{u'_j u'_m} \epsilon_{ikm} + \overline{u'_i u'_m} \epsilon_{jkm}) + S_{user} \end{aligned} \quad (6.18)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{Local Time Derivative} + C_{ij} = D_{T,ij} + D_{L,ij} + P_{ij} + G_{ij} + \phi_{ij} - \epsilon_{ij} + F_{ij} + \text{User-defined source term}$$

where, C_{ij} is the Convection-term, $D_{T,ij}$ is the Turbulent-diffusion term and $D_{L,ij}$ is the Molecular diffusion term, P_{ij} is the Production term, G_{ij} is the Buoyancy term, ϕ_{ij} the Pressure strain term, ϵ_{ij} the Dissipation term and F_{ij} is the Production due to rotation. Of these terms, C_{ij} , $D_{L,ij}$, P_{ij} and F_{ij} do not need modelling, the remaining terms $D_{T,ij}$, G_{ij} , ϕ_{ij} and ϵ_{ij} require modelling to close all the set of equations involved. Modelling of $D_{T,ij}$ is done by the simplified gradient-diffusion model using a scalar turbulent diffusivity in the following manner.

$$D_{T,ij} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \frac{\partial \overline{u'_i u'_j}}{\partial x_k} \right) \quad (6.19)$$

where μ_t is the turbulent diffusivity and $\sigma_k = 0.82$ is a constant for RSM models, that was given by Lien & Leschziner^[142]. The Pressure strain term is important, as it promotes the isotropy of the turbulence by redistributing the turbulent energy in all the directions. It is caused due to the interaction between the eddies and also due to the interaction of eddies with regions having a different mean velocity. It is modelled by decomposing the pressure strain term ϕ_{ij} into three new terms

$$\phi_{ij} = \phi_{ij,1} + \phi_{ij,2} + \phi_{ij,w} \quad (6.20)$$

where $\phi_{ij,1}$ is known as the slow-pressure strain term or *Return to Isotropy* term, $\phi_{ij,2}$ is the rapid-pressure strain term and $\phi_{ij,w}$ is the wall reflection term. The wall reflection term is responsible for the redistribution of Reynolds stress near the wall. It dampens the stresses normal to the wall and enhances the stresses parallel to the wall. The modelling of these terms can also be done by employing low Reynolds number corrections.

The Buoyancy term is modelled as,

$$G_{ij} = \beta \frac{\mu_t}{Pr_t} \left(g_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + g_j \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (6.21)$$

where Pr_t is the turbulent Prandtl number and β is the coefficient of thermal expansion. Finally, the dissipation term ϵ_{ij} is modelled assuming that the smallest dissipative eddies are isotropic. It is therefore modelled in the following way^[143]

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \frac{2}{3} \epsilon \delta_{ij} \quad (6.22)$$

As mentioned earlier, by not assuming isotropy, RSM is more accurate than EVM. It is also the most general model of turbulence and is therefore suitable for most of the problems related to turbulence. On the downside, RSM is significantly more expensive. Like all RANS models, RSM calculates the averaged values which do not simulate the actual turbulent condition for FSI problems.

6.3.4. Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes

Given that RANS averages the solution over the entire time, we can only hope to accurately simulate steady flows. For turbulent flows, which have fluctuating flow solutions over time, simple RANS would not give accurate solutions. An improvement on RANS that is capable of capturing transient behaviour is Unsteady RANS (URANS). The difference resides in the concept of the time step. In essence, if the RANS equations are solved with one global time step, which is used in every mesh cell, and if the value of the time step is small enough then we will be able to capture fluctuations, or unsteady behaviour in the *mean* quantities. As URANS models compute time averaged quantities of the flow (for each time step) such as velocity, pressure and temperature, very little information on the fluctuating quantities is available. The useful turbulent quantities available are turbulent kinetic energy (k), the energy dissipation rate (ϵ) and Reynolds shear stress tensor. As far as capturing VIV is concerned, it is shown that URANS does hold the capability to capture the oscillations of a single cylinder in cross-flow.^[144] For TIV, however, URANS has been deemed insufficient to capture the flow phenomena. To improve the same, Pressure Fluctuation Models (PFM) have been developed and implemented that aid in capturing the velocity and pressure fluctuations left out by URANS.^{[145],[146]}

6.4. Discretization of Governing Equations

Once the partial differential equations (PDEs) governing the physics of the fluids, structures and their interactions have been derived, they need to be discretized both in space and time to get a system of algebraic equations. These systems are then solved to get an approximate solution of the governing equations. Although discretization is necessary to compute a non-trivial solution of PDEs, they do introduce an additional source of error. The requirements for an acceptable discretization scheme are^[147]

- *Consistency*: Consistency of a numerical scheme implies that the numerical scheme must approach the differential equation when the time and space step sizes approach zero.
- *Stability*: A numerical scheme is considered stable if all the errors (such as round-off errors) remain bounded as the solution is marched forward in time. This implies that for finite values of time step size (Δt) and spatial element size (Δx), the error in the solution (defined as the difference between the numerical solution and the exact solution of the PDE) must remain bounded when the number of time marching steps tend to infinity.
- *Convergence*: A numerical scheme is said to converge if the numerical solution tends to the exact solution of the mathematical model that has been discretized, when the time step and the spatial step size tend to zero.

All three of the above conditions are related to each other through the *Equivalence Theorem of Lax* which states that “for a consistent finite difference method for a well-posed linear initial value problem, the method is convergent if and only if it is stable”.^[148]

6.4.1. Spatial Discretization

Spatial discretization refers to the process of converting the continuous spatial domain with infinite solution points into a discrete domain with finite number of solution points. This process results in a computational mesh on which the governing equations are solved. This is done to have an accurate enough representation of the real system while bounding the amount of computations that need to be done.

For fluid dynamics, the Finite Volume Method (FVM) is the most commonly used, whereas the Finite Element Method (FEM) is commonly used for structural dynamics. The computational mesh so created consists of nodes, edges and cell-faces. Different types of mesh can be used and are categorized according to their connectivity. In case of fully structured meshes, the connectivity between different cells is done in a ordered way and hence does not need to be stored explicitly, whereas for unstructured meshes, the connectivity between neighboring cells needs to be stored. The examples of these are shown in Figure 6.2. Another way of categorizing the types of mesh is based on where the unknown variables are stored on the computational grid. This is shown in Figure 6.3.

Figure 6.2: (a) Fully structured, (b) Fully structured with linear transformation and (c) Unstructured triangular mesh^[134]

Figure 6.3: (a) Cell centered variables (b) Node centered variables (c) Node and Cell centered variables (semi-staggered) (d) Variables with vectorial values at cell faces (fully-staggered)^[134]

6.4.2. Temporal Discretization

After discretizing the spatial derivatives of the PDE, we obtain an ordinary differential equation of the form

$$\frac{du}{dt} = F(u) \quad (6.23)$$

The above equation is referred to as semi-discretized form of the governing equation. Using the method of lines, time and space can be discretized separately. Time marching can be used to obtain a time accurate solution to a transient problem or to obtain a steady state solution following a time-independent path.^[149]

6.4.2.1. Explicit Time Integration

In explicit methods, the solution at the new time level $n + 1$ is only a function of known data at previous time levels, i.e,

$$u^{n+1} = f(u^n, u^{n-1}, u^{n-2}, \dots) \quad (6.24)$$

and therefore advancing in time is simple. The simplest example is *Forward Euler* (or Explicit Euler), where forward difference discretization in time is used and other terms are evaluated at the current time level t^n . Equation 6.23 is then approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u^{n+1} - u^n}{\Delta t} &= F(u^n) \\ \Rightarrow u^{n+1} &= u^n + \Delta t F(u^n) \end{aligned} \quad (6.25)$$

All explicit methods have a stability criterion for a time step above which instabilities occur. This means that all explicit methods should use small time steps which increases the computational cost.

6.4.2.2. Implicit Time Integration

In implicit methods, the solution at the new time level $n + 1$ is also a function of data at the new time level

$$u^{n+1} = f(u^{n+1}, u^n, u^{n-1}, u^{n-2}, \dots) \quad (6.26)$$

and more complicated strategies are required to solve for u^{n+1} than with explicit methods. The simplest example is *Backward Euler* (or Implicit Euler), where forward difference discretization in time is used and other terms are evaluated at the new time level t^{n+1} . Equation 6.23 is then approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u^{n+1} - u^n}{\Delta t} &= F(u^{n+1}) \\ \Rightarrow u^{n+1} &= u^n + \Delta t F(u^{n+1}) \end{aligned} \quad (6.27)$$

Implicit methods do not suffer from instability like explicit methods. This means that one can take as large a time step as possible. However, from the Taylor series expansion, one would be quick to realize that the error goes up with increasing time steps.

6.4.2.3. Higher Order Schemes

The order of accuracy of a scheme can be derived by looking at the truncation error of the discretization. The truncation error is obtained by substituting the exact solution into the numerical scheme and using Taylor series expansion to compare it with the original differential equation. The idea of higher order methods is to construct a scheme in which all lower order terms cancel to make the method converge faster to the exact solution. A simple example is given by the θ -method which is actually a linear combination of the forward and backward Euler method:

$$\theta\text{-method} = (1 - \theta)\text{FE} + \theta\text{BE} \quad (6.28)$$

The θ -method with the special choice $\theta = 0.5$ which is known as the *Crank-Nicolson scheme*, or the *trapezoidal rule*, is second order accurate.

6.4.2.4. Multi-step Methods

In multi-step methods, not only the solution at t^n is used to obtain the new solution at t^{n+1} but also previous solutions at t^{n-1} , t^{n-2} , etc. With a clever combination of time levels, one can make a scheme of arbitrary order of accuracy. The simplest example is the three level method (Leapfrog method) given by

$$\frac{u^{n+1} - u^{n-1}}{2\Delta t} = F(u^n) \quad (6.29)$$

One of the disadvantages of the multi-step methods is the *start-up problem*. In order to calculate the solution at t^1 , we need not only the initial solution at t^0 , but also the solution at t^{-1} or earlier and these solutions are not known. This can be fixed by using an appropriate lower order multi-step method in the first time-steps.

6.4.2.5. Multi-stage Methods

Multi-stage methods do not use more previous time levels, but the solution at intermediate time levels (stages) $t^n + \alpha$, $0 < \alpha < 1$ to obtain higher order accuracy in time. A linear combination of these solutions at intermediate stages is used to obtain a higher order accurate solution at t^{n+1} . The computation of the solution at the intermediate time levels can be done either in an implicit or explicit way.

The intermediate stage solutions u^k in Explicit Runge-Kutta (ERK) schemes are calculated using the following formula

$$\frac{u^k - u^n}{\Delta t} = \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} a_{kj} F(u^j) \quad (6.30)$$

where the sum is taken over all previous stages. The update to the new time level is then obtained by

$$\frac{u^{n+1} - u^n}{\Delta t} = \sum_{j=1}^m b_j F(u^j) \quad (6.31)$$

In Implicit Runge-Kutta (IRK) schemes, a sum is taken over all stages including the current stage to obtain the intermediate stage solutions

$$\frac{u^k - u^n}{\Delta t} = \sum_{j=1}^k a_{kj} F(u^j) \quad (6.32)$$

This means that we have to solve a system of equations at each intermediate stage. The update to the new time level is the same as that of the explicit schemes (Equation 6.31). RK methods are self-starting but each time step is computationally expensive.

6.5. Coupling of Fluid and Structure Governing Equations

In nuclear reactors, the coupling between the structures and the fluid is usually strong. One of the parameters to quantify the strength of coupling is the density ratio of the solid to the fluid (ρ_s/ρ_f). The value of density ratio can vary from 8.24 (steel-water) to 0.82 (Steel-Lead Bismuth Eutectic). These values of density ratios correspond to strongly coupled systems and hence need a robust and efficient coupling algorithm to be able to handle higher amount of coupling instabilities.

There are broadly two approaches to couple the fluid and structure governing equations: the *monolithic approach* and the *partitioned approach*. In the monolithic approach, the full set of equations (for the fluid, the structure and the interface) is built and solved for simultaneously. This might be an inefficient technique for the following reasons:^[149]

- Fluid codes and structural codes are usually totally separate softwares each of which using its own optimized tools specific for the field. Building the full system requires integrating the codes which in practice leads to intricate and hard to maintain software.
- Solving the structural problem (often linear or smoothly non-linear) is usually much easier than solving the non-linear convective fluid equations. Mixing the fields in a monolithic scheme usually prohibits to solve the structural part at low cost.
- The time-scale of the phenomena appearing in the fluid and in the structure are often very different. Moreover, explicit time-integration schemes are often used in CFD whereas implicit schemes are much more efficient for the structure where smooth dynamics is usually taking place. Hence the time-step required to solve the fluid is usually significantly smaller than the required structural time-step. If a monolithic scheme is adopted, both fields have to be integrated with the smallest time-step, thereby incurring unnecessary computing cost.

In the partitioned approach, the system is set up individually for the fluid and the structure domain, while the coupling is established externally which involves mapping and exchange of data from domain to the other. In the partitioned approach, different ways of discretization both for space and time can be used for the fluid and structure domains, thus making it more suitable for coupling pre-existing CFD and CSM codes. Usually, the monolithic approach is able to handle greater coupling instabilities.^[150] However, new partitioned coupling approaches have been developed recently which extend the range of applicability of the partitioned coupling approach to cases with stronger coupling.^{[150],[151]}

In the industry, we are generally interested in the partitioned approach of coupling. In this approach, the domains are coupled at the interface by the *kinematic boundary conditions* (displacement and velocity of both materials are equal at the interface) and *dynamic boundary conditions* (traction at the interface of the structure is in equilibrium with that on the fluid side).

In this section, the fluid and the structural solver are represented as operators \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{S} respectively. The input-output variables for these operators are the kinematic values ‘ \mathbf{s} ’ which comprise of displacement and velocities, and the dynamic values ‘ \mathbf{f} ’ comprising of forces and stresses. Using a Dirichlet-Neumann decomposition, the flow equations are solved for a given displacement of the fluid-structure interface (Dirichlet boundary condition) and the structural equations are solved for a given traction distribution on the interface (Neumann boundary condition). The solvers can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{s} &= \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{f}) \\ \mathbf{f} &= \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{s})\end{aligned}\tag{6.33}$$

There exist different schemes to couple these solvers. The most notable of them are the serial and parallel schemes which have their own inherent drawbacks. To combat their shortcomings, Newton-Raphson schemes have also been developed. One such scheme is the IQN-ILS. Each of these schemes are discussed in the following sub-sections.

6.5.1. Block Gauss-Seidel

This is one of the most commonly used explicit coupling schemes. Explicit schemes are the ones where Equation 6.33 is solved a fixed number of times per time step. Hence the kinematic and dynamic boundary conditions are not strictly enforced. Such schemes are usually used for weakly coupled systems, where the interaction is dominated by either of the 2 domains. The steps involved in Block-Gauss-Seidel coupling are shown in algorithm 1 and also graphically in Figure 6.4. In this algorithm, the domain which is executed first works in an explicit manner, e.g. in the shown algorithm the fluid solver is executed first and takes the structural input from the last time step, whereas the structural solver uses the updated value of the fluid solver in an implicit way.

Algorithm 1: Block Gauss-Seidel Algorithm

```

1 for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$  do
2   solve  $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}^n) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}$ ;
3   map  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1}$  to structure domain;
4   Solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^{n+1}) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$ ;
5   map  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid domain;
6 end

```

Figure 6.4: Block Gauss-Seidel coupling algorithm^[134]

This coupling algorithm is first order accurate in time regardless of the order of time integration in the individual fluid and structural solvers. In this type of coupling, both the fluid and structural solver cannot run in parallel (inter-field parallelism) as one is called after the other and depends on the input of the other. Although intra-field parallelism, which means solving the equations of the solver in a parallel way, can be applied to this case. For a total amount of k computational resources distributed among the fluid (k_f) and the structural solver (k_s) such that $k = k_f + k_s$, the computational time for each FSI time step (c) is given by^[134]

$$c = \frac{m_f c_f}{k_f} + \frac{m_s c_s}{k_s} \quad (6.34)$$

where m_f and m_s are the number of sub-cycling steps for both the fluid and the structural solver, whereas c_f and c_s refer to computational time taken for each time step of the fluid and the structural solver individually. Sub-cycling allows to decouple the time step sizes required in the fluid and structural solver. Usually, the time step size for a fluid solver is smaller than that of the structural solver for stability reasons. In such cases, the multiple smaller time steps can be used for the fluid solver to advance it through one coupled time-step. No exchange of information occurs between the 2 solvers during sub-cycling. An optimal distribution of the computational resources for Gauss-Seidel coupling algorithm is given by^[134]

$$\frac{k_f}{k_s} = \sqrt{\frac{m_f c_f}{m_s c_s}} \quad (6.35)$$

which gives an optimal computational time for each coupled time step as^[134]

$$c_{opt} = \frac{m_f c_f + m_s c_s + 2\sqrt{m_f c_f m_s c_s}}{k} \quad (6.36)$$

6.5.2. Block Gauss-Jacobi

The steps involved in the Block Jacobi scheme have been shown in [algorithm 2](#) and have been graphically represented in [Figure 6.5](#). This coupling scheme allows for inter-field parallelism of solvers i.e. both the solvers can be run parallel to each other. Hence, to optimize the usage of computational resources, both the solvers should execute in approximately the same time. The computational time step for each FSI time step using this coupling scheme with inter-field parallelism is given by^[134]

$$c = \max\left(\frac{m_f c_f}{k_f}, \frac{m_s c_s}{k_s}\right) \quad (6.37)$$

The optimal distribution of computational resources for this method is given by^[134]

$$\frac{k_f}{k_s} = \frac{m_f c_f}{m_s c_s} \quad (6.38)$$

which gives an optimum computational runtime for each coupled time step of size^[134]

$$c_{opt} = \frac{m_f c_f + m_s c_s}{k} \quad (6.39)$$

Algorithm 2: Block Gauss-Jacobi Algorithm

```

1 for  $n = 0$  to  $n_{end}$  do
2   solve  $\mathbf{F}^n(\mathbf{s}^n) = \mathbf{f}^{n+1}$ ;
3   Solve  $\mathbf{S}^n(\mathbf{f}^n) = \mathbf{s}^{n+1}$ ;
4   map  $\mathbf{f}^{n+1}$  to structure domain;
5   map  $\mathbf{s}^{n+1}$  to fluid domain;
6 end

```

Figure 6.5: Block Gauss-Jacobi coupling algorithm^[134]

6.5.3. Newton Raphson Schemes (IQN-ILS)

In this section, the input variables for the fluid and the structural solver are written as $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{s}$ and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{f}$. With these definitions, the fluid and structural solver equations can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) \\ \mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{y}) \end{aligned} \quad (6.40)$$

The traction on the interface \mathbf{y} can be eliminated from the above set of equations, resulting in an equation with only kinematic variables (interface displacement in this case)

$$\mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{x} = 0 \quad (6.41)$$

Introducing a residual operator \mathbf{R} defined as

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I} \quad (6.42)$$

with \mathbf{I} being the identity operator of the required dimensions, yields a smaller equation with \mathbf{x} as the unknown

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad (6.43)$$

The goal is to minimize this residual or to find the zero of the above equation using Newton-Raphson iterations. The Jacobian of \mathbf{R} with respect to \mathbf{x} is further denoted by \mathbf{R}' and in each Newton iteration a linear system

$$\mathbf{R}'^k \Delta \mathbf{x}^k = -\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}^k) \quad (6.44)$$

is solved with $\Delta \mathbf{x}^k = \mathbf{x}^{k+1} - \mathbf{x}^k$. We need to approximate the Jacobian because the exact Jacobian of $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x})$ is unknown as both \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{S} are taken as black box functions and are therefore unavailable. In each iteration, the residual vector is calculated as the difference between the output of the structural solver ($\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^k$) and the input of the flow solver (x_f^k) i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}^k &= \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}^k) \\ &= \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^k) - \mathbf{x}^k \\ &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^k - \mathbf{x}^k \end{aligned} \quad (6.45)$$

The linear system of equations (Equation 6.44) has the same dimensions as the number of nodes at the fluid-structure interface, and this has to be solved in each iteration. Although the number of nodes at the fluid-structure interface is considerably lower than the individual flow or structure domain, the Jacobian matrix (\mathbf{R}') is usually dense. Hence the solution of this system of linear equations is computationally expensive for large simulations. Therefore, it is more advantageous to approximate the inverse of this Jacobian using the least squares method. In this way, the system of linear equations (Equation 6.44) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{x}^{k+1} = \mathbf{x}^k + \widehat{(\mathbf{R}'^k)^{-1}}(-\mathbf{r}^k) \quad (6.46)$$

It can be seen from the above equation that the approximation for the inverse of the Jacobian does not have to be calculated explicitly. Instead we need to calculate the product of this inverse Jacobian with the vector $-\mathbf{r}^k$. This vector is the difference between the desired residual i.e. 0 and the current residual \mathbf{r}^k and is denoted as $\Delta \mathbf{r} = 0 - \mathbf{r}^k = -\mathbf{r}^k$. The matrix-vector product is calculated from the information obtained during the previous iterations. The vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ and \mathbf{r} are available from the previous iterations, giving a set of residual vectors $[\mathbf{r}^k, \mathbf{r}^{k-1}, \dots, \mathbf{r}^1, \mathbf{r}^0]$ and a corresponding set of displacement vectors $[\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^k, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k-1}, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^1, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^0]$.

The difference between the vectors from the current iterations and the previous iteration is calculated repeatedly for every iteration, thus giving us the following vectors

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \mathbf{r}^{k-1} &= \mathbf{r}^k - \mathbf{r}^{k-1} \\ \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k-1} &= \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^k - \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k-1} \end{aligned} \quad (6.47)$$

This yields another set of vectors $\Delta \mathbf{r}^i = [\Delta \mathbf{r}^k, \Delta \mathbf{r}^{k-1}, \dots, \Delta \mathbf{r}^1, \Delta \mathbf{r}^0]$ and a corresponding set of vectors $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^i = [\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^k, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k-1}, \dots, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^1, \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^0]$. Each $\Delta \mathbf{r}^i$ corresponds to a $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^i$ and these vectors are stored as columns of the matrices

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}^k &= [\Delta \mathbf{r}^{k-1} \quad \Delta \mathbf{r}^{k-2} \quad \dots \quad \Delta \mathbf{r}^1 \quad \Delta \mathbf{r}^0] \\ \mathbf{W}^k &= [\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k-1} \quad \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k-2} \quad \dots \quad \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^1 \quad \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^0] \end{aligned} \quad (6.48)$$

Due to similarity between consecutive time steps, information from previous time steps can also be combined with the matrices \mathbf{V}^k and \mathbf{W}^k , giving (assuming at least q time steps have been performed)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}^k &= [\Delta \mathbf{V}^k \quad \Delta \mathbf{V}^n \dots \quad \Delta \mathbf{V}^{n-q+2} \quad \Delta \mathbf{V}^{n-q+1}] \\ \mathbf{W}^k &= [\Delta \mathbf{W}^k \quad \Delta \mathbf{W}^n \dots \quad \Delta \mathbf{W}^{n-q+2} \quad \Delta \mathbf{W}^{n-q+1}] \end{aligned} \quad (6.49)$$

The convergence of the problems is generally accelerated by including information from the previous time steps upto a certain number of time steps and can slow down again if even greater number of time steps are re-used. The optimal value of time steps reused (q) is problem dependent but the convergence of coupling iterations does not change significantly near the optimum value.

The number of columns in \mathbf{V}^k and \mathbf{W}^k is indicated with ν and is usually much smaller than the number of rows u . The vector $\Delta \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{0} - \mathbf{r}^k = -\mathbf{r}^k$ is approximated as the linear combination of the known $\Delta \mathbf{r}^i$

$$\Delta \mathbf{r} \approx \mathbf{V}^k \mathbf{c}^k \in \mathcal{R} \quad (6.50)$$

with $\mathbf{c}^k \in \mathcal{R}^{\nu \times 1}$ as the coefficients of decomposition. Since ν is less than u , this system is over determined for the coefficients of decomposition \mathbf{c}^k , hence the least squares solution to this system is calculated. For this the economy-size QR-decomposition of \mathbf{V}^k is calculated using Householder transformations^[152]

$$\mathbf{V}^k = \mathbf{Q}^k \mathbf{R}^k \quad (6.51)$$

Now the coefficient \mathbf{c}^k can be determined by solving

$$\mathbf{R}^k \mathbf{c}^k = \mathbf{Q}^{kT} \Delta \mathbf{r} \quad (6.52)$$

The $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}$ corresponding to $\Delta \mathbf{r}$ are calculated in a similar way as a linear combination of known $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^i$

$$\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{W}^k \mathbf{c}^k \quad (6.53)$$

Using Equation 6.45, we can write

$$\Delta \mathbf{r} = \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{x}} - \Delta \mathbf{x} \quad (6.54)$$

Using Equation 6.53 and Equation 6.54, we get

$$\Delta \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{W}^k \mathbf{c}^k - \Delta \mathbf{r} \quad (6.55)$$

Using $\Delta \mathbf{r} = -\mathbf{r}^k$,

$$\Delta \mathbf{x} = \widehat{(\mathbf{R}^k)^{-1}} (-\mathbf{r}^k) = \mathbf{W}^k \mathbf{c}^k + \mathbf{r}^k \quad (6.56)$$

The overall algorithm has been summarized in algorithm 3.

Algorithm 3: IQN-ILS Algorithm^[153]

```

1 k=0;
2  $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^0 = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^0)$ ;
3  $\mathbf{r}^0 = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^0 - \mathbf{x}^0$ ;
4 while  $\|\mathbf{r}^k\|_2 > \epsilon_0$  do
5   if  $k = 0$  and ( $q = 0$  or  $n = 0$ ) then
6      $\mathbf{x}^{k+1} = \mathbf{x}^k + \omega \mathbf{r}^k$ ;
7   else
8     Construct  $\mathbf{V}^k$  and  $\mathbf{W}^k$ ;
9     Calculate Q-R decomposition  $\mathbf{V}^k = \mathbf{Q}^k \mathbf{R}^k$ ;
10    Solve  $\mathbf{R}^k \mathbf{c}^k = \mathbf{Q}^{kT} \Delta \mathbf{r}$ ;
11     $\mathbf{x}^{k+1} = \mathbf{x}^k + \mathbf{W}^k \mathbf{c}^k + \mathbf{r}^k$ ;
12  end
13   $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k+1} = \mathbf{S} \circ \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}^k)$ ;
14   $\mathbf{r}^{k+1} = \tilde{\mathbf{x}}^{k+1} - \mathbf{x}^{k+1}$ ;
15   $k++$ ;
16 end
```

6.5.4. Stability of Coupling Schemes

One of the major problems encountered during partitioned coupling approach is the instability created due to the partitioning. The staggered use of individual solvers i.e. using an explicit prediction for the boundary values at the interface in either one or both the solvers causes these instabilities. Regardless of how the individual solvers are set up, the above procedure introduces explicitness into the overall scheme. This section summarizes a few stability analyses found in literature.

In the work by Förster et. al.,^[154] a mathematical stability analysis is performed for explicit coupling schemes. A few conclusions of the article are: (a) instabilities decrease when structural stiffness is increased, (b) instabilities increase with increase in fluid viscosity, (c) higher order time integration methods lead to greater instabilities and (d) instabilities increase with decreasing time step. The last conclusion is contrary to the usual behavior of explicit schemes. Degroote et al.^[155] performed a stability analysis on a pipe-flow problem described in the work of Causin et. al.^[156] for implicit coupling schemes. Von Neumann stability analysis was performed to get the modal decomposition of the error in the displacement at the interface. It was observed that the low wave number error modes caused the most instabilities during the coupling iterations. Decreasing the structural stiffness or the time step being used resulted in a greater number of coupling iterations.

6.6. Mapping of Data

In FSI problems, it is often the case that the fluid mesh is considerably more refined than the structural mesh. The cells at the interface of the two domains are thus non-conformal and there is a need to map the data from one mesh to the other, such as the displacement from the structural domain to the fluid domain and the forces from the fluid domain onto the structural domain. This mapping could be *consistent* or *conservative*. In the consistent approach, a constant displacement or force is interpolated in such a way that it remains constant over the other domain too, whereas the conservative approach is based on the principle of conservation of energy at the interface. Two commonly used methods of data mapping are discussed below.

6.6.1. Nearest Neighbor Mapping

This is the simplest way of mapping data from one mesh to the other. Assuming data is to be transferred from mesh A to mesh B, this approach finds closest point in mesh A (x_A) for every point (x_B) of mesh B and assigns the value at x_A to x_B . A graphical depiction of this method is shown in Figure 6.6.

Figure 6.6: Nearest Neighbor data mapping algorithm^[134]

6.6.2. Radial Basis Function Mapping

In this method, the quantity to be transferred from mesh A to mesh B is approximated as a sum of basis functions using the known data from nodes of mesh A. The interpolant thus created is then evaluated at the nodes of mesh B. The interpolant can be written as

$$\mathbf{w}_i(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_A} \gamma_j \phi(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{A_j}\|) + \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{x}), \quad i = A, B \quad (6.57)$$

where \mathbf{x}_{A_j} are the coordinates of the nodes where the value to be interpolated is already known, ϕ is the given radial basis function evaluated at any given euclidean distance $\|\mathbf{x}\|$. The coefficients γ_j and the polynomial \mathbf{q} can be evaluated using the interpolation condition

$$\mathbf{w}_A(\mathbf{x}_{A_j}) = \mathbf{W}_A \quad (6.58)$$

where \mathbf{W}_A is a vector containing the known discrete values (\mathbf{w}_A) at the interface of mesh A. An additional requirement is

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_A} \gamma_j s(\mathbf{x}_{A_j}) = 0 \quad (6.59)$$

for all polynomials s with a degree less than or equal to q . The above two conditions can be combined and written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_A \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{AA} & Q_A \\ Q_A^T & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \gamma \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.60)$$

where γ refers to γ_j , β represents the coefficients of polynomial \mathbf{q} , ϕ_{AA} is a matrix containing evaluation of basis function $\phi_{A_i A_j} = \phi(\|\mathbf{x}_{A_i} - \mathbf{x}_{A_j}\|)$. To get the data formesh B, the interpolant is evaluated at the nodes of mesh B interface.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}_B &= [\phi_{BA} \quad Q_B] \begin{bmatrix} \gamma \\ \beta \end{bmatrix} \\ &= [\phi_{BA} \quad Q_B] \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{AA} & Q_A \\ Q_A^T & 0 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}_A \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (6.61)$$

6.7. Conclusion

In this chapter, the most important numerical concepts concerning FSI problems have been reviewed and summarized. This includes the frame of reference that is most beneficial for FSI problems, the differential equations governing the phenomena being studied, turbulence modelling, the discretization methods for both space and time, and the coupling techniques at the interface of two different domains. Monolithic and partitioned coupling approaches were briefly discussed, while different types of partitioned coupling approaches and their stability were also discussed. Finally, a short overview of the most common data mapping algorithms was provided.

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